

ExtremeXP

Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

D2.2: Final architecture, traceability, and trustworthiness for complex experiment-driven analytics

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Abstract	This deliverable details on the final version of the meta-model describing the experimentation process for optimizing complex analytics as well as on the final version of a probabilistic approach that provides recommendations via options ranking from knowledge of previous experiments. It also presents the decentralized access control mechanism that forms the foundation for the trustworthiness and traceability layer of the ExtremeXP framework. Finally, it describes the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework, both from a structural and behavioural viewpoint.
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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
ABI	Arbitrary Binary Interface
ACI	Access Control Interface
DAL	Data Abstraction Layer
DDM	Distributed Data Management
DDM	Decentralized Data Management
DSL	Domain-Specific language
ECDSA	Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm
EE	Execution Engine
EIP	Ethereum Improvement Proposal
EMF	Eclipse Modelling Framework
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IPFS	InterPlanetary File System
LLM	Large Language Model
LSP	Language Server Protocol
MDP	Markov Decision Process
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
UI	User interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VSC	Visual Studio Code
WTA	Web Testing Application

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final version of the foundations for experiment-driven analytics established within the ExtremeXP project. It first details on the final version of the meta-model describing the experimentation process for optimizing complex analytics, as well as on the final version of a probabilistic approach that provides recommendations via options ranking from knowledge of previous experiments. The deliverable then presents the implementation and evaluation of the decentralized access control mechanism that forms the foundation for the trustworthiness and traceability layer of the ExtremeXP framework. Finally, it describes the final software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework, both from a structural and behavioural viewpoint.

1 Introduction

The objective of WP2 is to provide the modelling and language foundations for experiment-driven analytics focusing on software variability aspects, experiment specification, and context. It also provides the foundations for the trustworthiness and traceability layer and the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework. This deliverable reports on the following tasks of WP2, providing an update to the description of the previous deliverable of this work package, i.e., D2.1 “Initial architecture, languages and models for complex experiment-driven analytics” [AAB+24]:

T2.1 Experimentation modelling with domain specific modelling languages (Section 2)

The focus on this task was on creating the meta-model and associated domain specific language (DSL) for specifying complex analytics workflows (CAWs) and experiments.

As defined in D2.1, a CAW is an abstraction over different types of data-driven analytics workflows that includes (possibly combinations of):

1. machine learning (ML) training workflows;
2. job scheduling and task automation workflows;
3. simulation-based workflows, i.e., chaining of simulation models;
4. data analysis scripts, as developed, e.g., by data analysts using notebooks;
5. extract-transform-load (ETL) pipelines found in data warehousing technologies;
6. scientific workflows like what can be developed with, e.g., Apache Taverna.

Although CAW is a general concept that can be reified in any of the above, the ExtremeXP use cases feature mostly options 1, 3, and 4, i.e., ML training workflows, simulation-based workflows, and data analysis scripts. For simplicity, we refer to CAWs in this deliverable as just “workflows”.

An “experiment” in ExtremeXP, as defined also in D2.1, is a concept to systematically develop, automate, reuse, setup, execute, track, explain, compare, and optimize CAWs.

Experiments and workflows can be specified by data analysts and data engineers using a quite expressive DSL, which is itself based on the unified ExtremeXP EMF-based meta-model – both of which are entirely developed within the project. As detailed in Section 2, regarding specifying workflows, the DSL allows for capturing control and data flow between tasks in a workflow, composite tasks leading to hierarchical workflows, parameters of tasks, outputs and metrics generated by tasks and structural variability via alternative implementations of abstract workflow tasks. When it comes to experiments, the DSL provides constructs for modelling of sequential and parallel experiment steps, different exploration strategies in experiments (exploring both the structural and parametric variability), conditional execution of experimental tasks, and interactive experiment-level tasks (where the user in the loop can intervene and influence the execution of an experiment). In ExtremeXP, the DSL for experiments and workflows can be either provided by end users or produced in an automated manner from intents [BJN+25].

T2.2 Semantically rich context representation and probabilistic meta-analysis (Section 3)

The goal of this task was to give a semantic representation of experiments and also investigate methods to learn from past experiments (meta-analysis). Concretely, this led to the development of the Options Explorer component of the ExtremeXP architecture. The Options Explorer is a recommendation service for experiments. Given (1) certain information about the datasets to be used as input, (2) the intent for the workflow under experimentation (e.g. training of ML classifier), and (3) any constraints that the user imposes (e.g. “the accuracy of produced ML model more than 90%”), it recommends algorithms (e.g. neural network) and/or models (e.g. particular architecture of neural network) to be evaluated in an experiment. Internally, the component relies on knowledge graphs for

representing the experiment-related knowledge and Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) for analysis and reasoning. When integrated with the rest of the ExtremeXP framework, the Options Explorer is connected to the Intents editor and allows users to skip the evaluation of options (i.e. workflow variants) that are less probable of yielding good results (relevant to the soft constraint or optimization goals of the user) based on past knowledge. This leads to an overall more efficient experimentation process.

T2.3 Traceability and trustworthiness for experiment-driven analytics (Section 4)

This task focused on protecting resources on the ExtremeXP framework using a context-aware access control mechanism. This can be done for both centralized and decentralized deployments of the ExtremeXP framework. For the latter, a fine-grained Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is implemented as a smart contract on a blockchain (Hyperledger Besu). Section 4 details both the implementation and the evaluation of this mechanism. On top of this result, T2.3 contributed an NFT-based data provenance mechanism which was detailed in D2.1. Overall, the results of this task, together with the results of T5.4 and T5.5, were reified in four of the five components of the knowledge management module of the ExtremeXP framework (Figure 27): Access control, Distributed Dataset Management, Experiment cards, and NFT-based data provenance. Collectively, they provide guarantees for the secure execution of experiments, where data analysis and data engineers running those experiments have access to only the resources they are permitted to access, enhancing trustworthiness and transparency.

T2.4 Software and reference architecture for complex experiment-driven analytics (Section 5)

The objective of this task was dual: on the one side, iteratively design and develop the software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework; on the other side, distil and provide a set of guidelines and best practices in the form of a reference architecture. Section 5 provides an account on both. First, the framework architecture is described both from a structural viewpoint (sub-systems or modules and components contained in them) and from a behavioural viewpoint (interactions between components and modules). This is an update on the architecture described in D2.1 at the end of the first year of the project. Although many modules and components remained intact, in the last two years of the projects the architecture organically evolved, following the enhanced understanding of its users (the ExtremeXP partners) on how the components they develop fit in the overall vision of experiment-driven analytics of ExtremeXP. Second, in Section 5 we also detail the work that was conducted towards deriving a reference architecture for MLOPs. We chose to focus on MLOPs since it is an established domain with several emerging practices that we could extract and analyse. This is contrary to the “complex experiment-driven and user-driven analytics” domain which is hard to define. Still, given the several connections between the two domains, the outcome and the take-aways of the MLOPs analysis is also relevant for building better experiment-driven and user-driven analytics.

2 Experimentation Modelling and Meta-model

This section presents the final version of the ExtremeXP experimentation meta-model and its accompanying modelling approach, completing the evolution initiated in Deliverable D2.1 [AAB+24] and refined through the implementation work reported in D5.1 [AHB+25] and D5.2 [KGR+24]. The meta-model now provides a unified and operational foundation for describing workflows, tasks, control-flow structures, variability points, data flows, experiment spaces, and complete experiment configurations in a form that is both semantically precise and directly consumable by the ExtremeXP toolchain.

The final model consolidates the requirements that emerged from the development of the DSL framework, the language server, the graphical editors, and the experimentation engine. In particular,

the formal abstractions for composite workflows, assembled workflows, parameterization mechanisms, metrics, and human-in-the-loop interactions have been aligned with the concrete execution semantics implemented in the Experimentation Engine (D5.1) and the workflow-centric DSL tooling (D5.2). The result is a stable modelling core that supports round-trip transformations between DSL specifications, graphical representations, and runtime artefacts.

2.1 Overview of achieved results

During the final phase of the project, the modelling foundations of ExtremeXP were brought to their final, operational form. The work focused on stabilizing the meta-model introduced in D2.1 and aligning it with the concrete requirements that emerged from the development of the DSL framework, the language server, the graphical editors, and the Experimentation Engine, as reported in D5.1 and D5.2. This required consolidating the conceptual model, completing missing abstractions, and ensuring full compatibility with the execution semantics needed by the runtime environment.

A key result is the adoption of a single, unified meta-model describing both workflows and experiments. This meta-model now captures the complete range of ExtremeXP concepts: composite workflows, assembled workflows, task specifications, operators, data links, parameters and value domains, metrics, experiment spaces, and experiment-level control structures. Its expressiveness and granularity were validated through all project use cases and through the implementation of the DSL and the graphical editors. The meta-model, therefore, serves as the stable core for all modelling activities and tools in the framework.

The meta-model and DSL also clarify how to express two types of variability: parametric and structural. Parametric variability focuses on changing parameter values or settings within an experiment, while structural variability focuses on changing the arrangement of tasks or workflow components. By supporting both forms of variability, the meta-model and DSL together let modelers define experiments that adjust their parameters as well as their workflow structure.

To make the meta-model usable in practice, a dedicated modelling toolchain was completed. A human-readable DSL, defined directly on top of the meta-model, was finalized and covers constructs for workflow composition, variability, experiment configuration, and parameter exploration. A language server, integrated with the DSL and exposed via the Language Server Protocol (LSP), enables real-time validation, cross-reference resolution, and semantic checks in Integrated Development Environments (IDEs). This server powers the web-based DSL editor (developed as a VSCode extension), which allows for developing experiments, workflows, etc., and can be simultaneously used by multiple users, thus enabling easy cooperation on experimentation projects.

Complementing the textual DSL, the web-based graphical workflow and experiment editors were finalized and stabilized. These editors generate meta-model-compliant artifacts and support round-trip engineering: DSL \leftrightarrow meta-model \leftrightarrow graphical representation. This required completing the conversion layer between JSON, XMI, and DSL syntaxes, ensuring that models remain structurally identical regardless of the editing modality.

Finally, the integration of the meta-model with the Experimentation Engine (D5.1) and the DSL tooling (D5.2) was completed. Workflows and experiments expressed in the DSL and/or graphically can now be parsed, validated, transformed into executable workflow graphs, and deployed within the Experimentation Engine without manual intervention. This confirms that the meta-model is not only expressive and well-structured but also fully operational and aligned with the overall ExtremeXP architecture.

Overall, the achieved results provide a mature, consistent, and implementation-validated modelling foundation for the ExtremeXP framework, supporting reproducible, traceable, and configurable experiment-driven analytics across all use cases.

2.2 Detailed walkthrough of the latest version of the models/tools/approaches

2.2.1 Meta-model

The ExtremeXP meta-model provides the conceptual backbone for expressing workflows, tasks, data flows, experiment configurations, and variability in a uniform and machine-interpretable form. While D2.1 introduced the initial structure, the final version presented here reflects the requirements derived from the full implementation cycle of WP5 (D5.1, D5.2) and the integration work across the toolchain. Nevertheless, the updates (in relation to D2.1) are subtle and do not introduce any major change in the meta-model.

At its core, the meta-model defines a coherent set of abstractions for describing complex analytics processes, including workflows composed of tasks and operators, explicit data links that capture the flow of information, parameter definitions with constrained domains, metric specifications, and higher-level experiment constructs such as experiment spaces and control-flow nodes. These abstractions were shaped not only by the theoretical modelling needs of WP2 but also by practical demands from the DSL framework, the language server, the graphical editors, and the experimentation engine, all of which rely on the metamodel as the authoritative source of structural and semantic truth.

The resulting model strikes a balance between expressive power and operational clarity. It is expressive enough to capture heterogeneity—different task implementations, nested workflows, parameterizable components, and human-in-the-loop interactions—yet precise enough to support static validation, automatic transformation into DSL syntax, and generation of executable workflow artifacts. In the remainder of this section, we detail the elements of the metamodel, explain their roles and interrelations, and outline how they collectively underpin experiment specification and execution throughout the ExtremeXP ecosystem.

The metamodel (as well as most parts of the DSL framework) is designed and implemented using the Eclipse Modelling Framework (EMF). The implementation itself is available at <https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-workflow-metamodel>.

In the rest of this section, we describe the individual elements of the metamodel. The description is based on the text of D2.1 [AAB+24] and D5.2 [KGR+24].

2.2.1.1 Meta-model definition

We use the terms “model” and “meta-model” as they have been defined by OMG [OMG14]. The model “is information selectively representing some aspect of a system based on a specific set of concerns”, and the meta-model describes what can be used in a model. The meta-model describes the basic concepts of the workflow and the relationships of the concepts. In the text that accompanies the respective parts of the meta-model, we further explain the semantics of the concepts.

For the visualisation of the meta-model itself, we use a subset of UML class diagrams. For better readability of the text, we omit the “meta” prefix when describing the meta-model elements (i.e., meta-class is referred to as a class, meta-attribute as an attribute, etc.).

The figure in Appendix A (the figure is separately in the appendix in order to allow including it in high resolution) shows the complete meta-model (without the user interface (UI) related elements, as they are managed separately and described in [KNN+25]). The figure is taken directly from the EMF meta-model editor, and thus it shows the actual and current status of the meta-model as it is used in the implementation.

The subsections below describe the individual elements (grouped by their semantic relations).

2.2.1.2 Workflow elements

The entry to this is the abstract Workflow class. The Workflow defines a name of the workflow and refers to the InputData and OutputData. The InputData and OutputData are named, but they are not further modelled, i.e., they are considered unstructured blocks.

There are three concrete children of the Workflow: TaskSpecification, CompositeWorkflow, and AssembledWorkflow.

The TaskSpecification represents a “primitive” workflow that consists of a single executable task. It defines its implementation (e.g., a Python script or another executable) via the Task class (see below) and a set of configuration parameters. Additionally, the TaskSpecification may compute a number of Metrics as a part of its execution. These typically represent some summary statistics that characterize a dataset that Task operates on or has produced (e.g., the accuracy of a created ML model) or that characterize the execution of the task itself (e.g., its throughput or performance).

The CompositeWorkflow represents a workflow composed of a set of tasks connected by operators. Technically, the CompositeWorkflow is composed of multiple Nodes, Links, and DataLinks. The nodes are Events (Start and End of a workflow), Tasks, and Operators. Links interconnect the Nodes. Operators allow for the branching of a workflow. DataLinks define data flow.

The Node class is abstract and represents a common parent for “actions” in a workflow. It has three children: Task, Connector, and Event. The Event represents a special action in the workflow. Currently, there are two possible events – the START of a workflow and the END of a workflow. The Task class represents an individual action in a workflow. It can have multiple data inputs and outputs. The Task is either a specific one with an explicitly defined implementation or an abstract one, i.e., without an actual implementation, which is later specified by the AssembledWorkflow (see below).

The Operator class represents forks and joins in a workflow. It is an abstract class and there are three possible forking operators and the single Join operator. The fork operators are as follows:

- Parallel operator – creates parallel paths of execution in a workflow. All the paths are executed potentially simultaneously.
- Exclusive operator – creates alternative paths of execution in a workflow. Only a single path is executed.
- Inclusive operator – creates alternative but possibly parallel paths in a workflow. It represents a combination of the Parallel and Exclusive operators; while the Parallel operator executes all the paths and the Exclusive operator executes a single path, here several paths can be chosen (based on the conditions) and executed in parallel.

The Link class represents links between nodes (Task, Event, or Operator). A link is an oriented connection between strictly two nodes – one is an input node, and another is an output node. The Link is an abstract class with three particular subclasses. They are as follows:

- RegularLink – is a regular, unconditional flow from one node in a workflow to another one.
- ConditionalLink – is a flow that is executed when an associated condition is satisfied. There must be multiple links from a particular node so that another flow can be selected when the condition is not satisfied.
- ExceptionalLink – is a flow that is taken when an exception occurs in a node execution. It is similar to the ConditionalLink, but the ExceptionalLink emphasizes that it handles an exception.

The Links and Operators together represent the control flow in the CompositeWorkflow. On the other hand, the DataLink represents the data flow in the CompositeWorkflow. i.e., how data is passed between the Tasks of the CompositeWorkflow.

The *Group* class enables the logical grouping of Tasks (i.e., to emphasize that several tasks are logically related) in the *CompositeWorkflow*.

The *Metadata* class models arbitrary additional information as a key-value pair. Thus, each piece of metadata has a name and a value. The name is hierarchical. The *MetaData* can be attached to Tasks or Groups of tasks.

The *ParameterType* class defines a type used for Parameters. It is an abstract class with three concrete subclasses representing a particular kind of type. These are (i) primitive types, (ii) arrays of a particular type, and (iii) structures. The Primitives are either numbers, Booleans (true, false), Strings, or unstructured binary large objects (BLOBs). Arrays and Structures have the traditional semantics.

The *AssembledWorkflow*, as the name suggests, represents a workflow assembled from other workflows. It is always based on another workflow, in which the *AssembledWorkflow* allows designers to configure the tasks – mainly to set the task’s implementation (in a workflow, a task’s implementation may not be set – it is then an abstract task, see above). The *SubstitutedTask* is then the configuration of an abstract task in the *AssembledWorkflow*.

2.2.1.3 Experiment elements

The *Experiment* class, as the name suggests, represents an experiment, which is, simply speaking, a configuration over multiple assembled workflows.

The *Experiment* defines a sequence of *ExperimentStep* elements that together form the overall experimentation process. These steps can take several forms: (i) exploration of an experiment space (*ExperimentSpace*), (ii) interaction with the user (represented by *Interaction*), and (iii) automated experiment-level tasks that run without user involvement.

The *ExperimentSpace* specifies a design space consisting of multiple parameterizations of a single *AssembledWorkflow*. Together with an exploration strategy, it determines how these parameterized workflow variants are enumerated and explored. Each variant is executed during this traversal, and its resulting metrics are collected and stored. In the project’s use cases, this mechanism is applied, for instance, to study how different neural network hyperparameters influence the resulting accuracy.

Examples of exploration strategies include grid search (which systematically generates all combinations of parameter values), random search (which samples combinations stochastically), and Bayesian optimization (which balances exploration and exploitation by considering expected improvement and uncertainty).

Consequently, one *AssembledWorkflow* can result in multiple concrete workflow executions.

The *Interaction* represents a step that invokes a task coupled with a user interface. Such a step provides a tailored, task-specific micro-frontend through which the user reviews the results collected so far and decides how the experiment should proceed.

Finally, the experiment specifies the order in which the *ExperimentSteps* are executed.

This control logic is described using the *Control*, *Execution*, and *ControlLink* classes (and their subclasses), which together allow a concise definition of the experiment’s structure.

2.2.1.4 Root Container

The *Root* class is a utility class that serves as a top-level container for other elements in the meta-model (the presence of the class simplifies usage of EMF).

2.2.2 DSL

2.2.2.1 DSL overview

Although the metamodel provides a formal definition of experiments and workflows, it is insufficient on its own. It is necessary to have a way to easily create the meta-model instances, i.e., the actual experiment and workflows definitions. Therefore, we designed a Domain Specific Language (DSL) to create them.

The DSL provides a structured way to describe workflows, tasks, experiments, and their interconnections in a uniform notation. At its core, it distinguishes between (i) workflows, which orchestrate multiple tasks and data flows, (ii) task specifications, which define reusable units with inputs, outputs, parameters, and implementations, and (iii) assembled workflows, which extend existing workflows by refining task configurations. Data definitions (inputs, outputs, and configurations) ensure that information exchange is explicit, while links and operators describe the logical and conditional flow between workflow components. In addition, parameters, metrics, and groups of tasks make the specification expressive enough to capture diverse experimental and workflow scenarios.

Beyond workflows, the DSL also provides constructs for describing experiments: spaces for parameter exploration, interactions consisting of actions, and control flows that guide execution. These experiment descriptions are tightly integrated with workflows, allowing spaces to bind to workflows and configure them with strategies, attributes, or further task refinements. The DSL is expressive but keeps a consistent structure, making it possible to combine declarative descriptions of workflows with more dynamic experimental design. The `SingleTaskW` workflow in Listing 1 represents the simplest possible executable workflow in the ExtremeXP DSL. It consists of a single task `Task1` (and two events `START` and `END`). The task is associated with a concrete implementation located at `"demo_tasks/TestOutput"`, which defines the executable logic for this task.

The workflow defines one input and one output dataset. The input dataset, `InputFile`, is connected to the `Task1.InputFile` port and is configured to read data from `"demo_datasets/demo_data.txt"`. The output dataset, `OutputFile`, is produced by `Task1.OutputFile` and is configured to be written to the directory `"output/trained_model/**"`. This pattern allows the workflow to take a fixed input, process it through a single task, and store the resulting output in a predefined location.

The workflow `SingleTaskAW2` is defined as an assembled workflow derived from `SingleTaskW`. Since `SingleTaskW` has no parameters configured, the `SingleTaskAW2` assembled workflow is empty. This illustrates the assembled workflow mechanism, where these workflows may selectively configure components of their base workflow (or, if no configuration is needed, they simply inherit the base workflow).

The `ExampleExpSimple` experiment demonstrates how such a workflow is executed within an experiment. The experiment here is straightforward, and its control flow only consists of a single experimentation space `S1`. The `S1` space is associated with the assembled workflow `SingleTaskAW2` and uses the `randomsearch` strategy to generate actual executable workflows from the definition. Since `SingleTaskAW2` contains no parameters or variability points, the random search strategy degenerates into the generation of a single executable workflow, which is then submitted to the Execution engine.

```
workflow SingleTaskW {
```

```
    task Task1 {
```



```
        implementation "demo_tasks/TestOutput";
    }

    START -> Task1 -> END;

    define input data InputFile;
    InputFile --> Task1.InputFile;
    configure data InputFile {
        path "demo_datasets/demo_data.txt";
    }

    define output data OutputFile;
    Task1.OutputFile --> OutputFile;
    configure data OutputFile {
        path "output/trained_model/**";
    }
}

workflow SingleTaskAW2 from SingleTaskW {
}

experiment ExampleExpSimple {
    control {
        START -> S1 -> END;
    }

    space S1 of SingleTaskAW2 {
        strategy randomsearch;
        runs = 1;
    }
}
```

Listing 1: Simple example of DSL

Listing 2 shows another example, this time with a more complex experiment definition (to save space, only the relevant parts of DSL are shown). It demonstrates how the DSL captures variability and human-in-the-loop decision points.

It begins with a generic workflow (ExampleWF) comprising four sequential tasks: data loading, preprocessing, splitting, and model training. The training step is intentionally left abstract (no implementation specified) so that different model families can be plugged in later.

Two assembled workflows (FDW1 and FDW2) specialize this generic workflow by assigning distinct implementations to the TrainModel task—one using a feed-forward neural network and the other a recursive neural network. Apart from this substitution, both variants inherit the same structure and dataflow from the base workflow.

The experiment (ExampleExperiment) coordinates the exploration of these workflow variants. It defines two coarse-grained search spaces; each associated with one of the assembled workflows and configured with ranges and enumerations for the training hyperparameters. After both coarse searches complete, the experiment pauses at a user-interaction step, where the user is shown intermediate results and can select the preferred model family. The control logic then branches accordingly, activating the fine-grained search space for the chosen workflow variant.

This example showcases how the DSL supports: (i) workflow variability through task substitution, (ii) structured exploration of parameter spaces, and (iii) explicit user decisions embedded in experiment control flow.

```
workflow ExampleWF {
  task ReadData {
    implementation "...";
  }
  task AddPadding {...}
  task SplitData {...}
  task TrainModel;

  // control flow
  START -> ReadData -> AddPadding -> SplitData -> TrainModel -> END;

  define input data ExternalDataFile;
  define output data ProducedModel;

  // data flow
  ExternalDataFile --> ReadData.ExternalDataFile;
  ReadData.X --> PrepareData.X1;
  ReadData.Y --> PrepareData.Y1;
  ...
  EvaluateModel.TrainedModel --> ProducedModel;
}
```

```
workflow FDW1 from ExampleWF {
  task TrainModel {
    implementation "...trainNN.py";
  }
}

workflow FDW2 from ExampleWF {
  task TrainModel {
    implementation "...trainRNN.py";
  }
}

experiment ExampleExperiment {
  control {
    START -> SNNCoarse -> SRNNCoarse -> UI1;
    UI1 -> SNNFine {condition selected NN};
    UI1 -> SRNNFine {condition selected RNN};
    SNNFine -> END;
    SRNNFine -> END;
  }

  space SNNCoarse of FDW1 {
    // coarse search over NN
    strategy gridsearch;
    param_values epochs_vp = range(60,120,20);
    param_values batch_size_vp = enum(64, 128);
    configure task TrainModel {
      param epochs = epochs_vp;
      param batch_size = batch_size_vp;
    }
  }

  space SRNNCoarse of FDW2 {
    // coarse search over RNN
    strategy gridsearch;
    param_values epochs_vp = range(60,120,20);
    param_values batch_size_vp = enum(64, 128);
  }
}
```

```
    task TrainModel {
        param epochs = epochs_vp;
        param batch_size = batch_size_vp;
    }
}
interaction UserInteraction {
    task choice(...);
}
space SNNFine of FDW1 {
    ...
}
space SRNNFine of FDW2 {
    ...
}
}
```

Listing 2: DSL example with a complex experiment

2.2.2.2 DSL implementation

From the implementation point of view, the DSL is a part of the DSL framework. Its implementation is available at <https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dsl-framework>. The framework consists of the DSL definition itself and the language server.

The DSL is defined using Xtext¹, which is a project related to EMF and allows for easy creation of DSL for meta-models. The complete grammar of our DSL is available here <https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dsl-framework/blob/main/eu.extremexp.dsl.parent/eu.extremexp.dsl/src/eu/extremexp/dsl/XDSL.xtext> (as the definition is rather large, we do not include it here). Details about the grammar are in Deliverable D5.1.

From the DSL grammar, the language server for our DSL is generated using Xtext. The language server is a background service that offers language-aware features such as autocompletion, error reporting, and refactoring support through the standard Language Server Protocol². Internally, Xtext converts the grammar into an EMF-compatible metamodel. We designed the DSL grammar so that the metamodel produced by Xtext aligns (almost) one-to-one with the core meta-model described above (there are a few very subtle technical differences, but from the usage point of view, they are invisible).

The generated language server is then utilized in a customized Visual Studio Code setup that integrates the generated language server, providing users with a modern editor for authoring workflows and experiments. Although our main editor is based on VSCode, the generated language server can be used with any IDE that supports the Language Server Protocol, which includes virtually all widely used development environments today.

¹ <https://eclipse.dev/Xtext/>

² <https://microsoft.github.io/language-server-protocol/>

Figure 1 shows a screenshot of our DSL editor. More information about it is in Deliverable D5.1.


```

1 workflow ComplexControlW {
2
3     task Task1 {
4         implementation "Testcase_task1";
5     }
6
7     task Task2;
8
9     START -> Task1 -> Task2 -> END;
10
11 }
12
13 workflow ComplexControlAW1 from ComplexControlW {
14     task Task2 {
15         implementation "Testcase_task2_v1";
16     }
17 }
18
19 workflow ComplexControlAW2 from ComplexControlW {
20     task Task2 {
21         implementation "Testcase_task2_v2";
22     }
23 }
24
25 experiment ComplexControlExp1 {
26     intent testComplexControl;
27
28     control {
29         START -> (S1 || S2);
30     }
31
32     space S1 of ComplexControlAW1 {
33         strategy gridsearch;
34         param param1_vp = enum(2, 5, 1);
35         task Task1 {
36             param param1 = param1_vp;
37         }

```

Figure 1: DSL editor screenshot

2.2.2.3 Graphical editors

To complete the section on modelling workflows and experiments, it is necessary to mention the graphical editors, which can be used in parallel with the DSL editor and also offer means to define workflows and experiments visually. The Workflow Designer, shown in Figure 2, supports the visual definition of workflows, while the Experiment Designer, shown in Figure 3, enables the visual specification of experiments. More details are available in Deliverable D5.1.

Figure 2: Workflow Designer

Figure 3: Experiment Designer

2.3 Comment on delta with respect to D2.1 and D5.1

The section summarizes changes made to the meta-model and DSL since they were first presented in Deliverables D2.1 (meta-model), D5.2 (DSL), and D5.1 (DSL framework and small updates to the meta-model). All changes were made based on the experience gained during the design and development of the DSL, the visual editor, and the experimentation engine, as well as on feedback from the use-case implementations and integration in WP6.

The changes in the meta-model are as follows:

- The original Workflow was remodelled into three separate classes (TaskSpecification, Composite, and Assembled Workflows) that explicitly distinguished a kind of workflow. The change was necessary to allow for easy reuse of already created workflows.
- The Complex operator was removed as we found no usage for it, and its precise semantics were unclear.
- The DataLink class (and its children) were added to explicitly model data flow. Also, thanks to the addition of the DataLink, we simplified the data representation (i.e., no need to distinguish external/internal data).
- The Deployment, ExperimentSpace, and UserIntent packages were removed, and their elements were completely remodelled and merged into the rest of the meta-model. The deployment related elements resulted in the AssembledWorkflow and parts in the Experiment description. The ExperimentSpace and UserIntent elements were remodelled into similar elements referred to from the Experiment.

The changes in DSL are as follows:

- The separate definitions of a task and its configuration in a Composite workflow were merged together (in order to make the DSL concise and more readable).
- Packages were made optional.
- The experiment definition was updated based on the changes in the meta-model (as described above).
- It is now possible to create an experiment in a different file and import the assembled workflows defined in different files with such statement “import <filename: String>;”.

3 Probabilistic Options Explorer

3.1 Overview

Within ExtremeXP, the Options Explorer places domain experts at the centre of complex analytics workflows that combine machine learning, data analysis, and simulation, together with their visualisations. It is designed for users who require actionable results but may lack advanced technical expertise in areas such as data management, machine learning, resource orchestration, or query languages. The workflow structures scientific experimentation as an iterative decision process, formalized as a modular sequence of states governed by a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and supported by feedback loops and a knowledge graph to maintain contextual continuity.

The process comprises three phases. In contextualisation, the user configures the experiment via a graphical interface by defining objectives, parameters, constraints, and operating conditions. In decision-making, the system applies probabilistic modelling to propose and rank options in accordance with the established context, providing formal assurances for each recommendation while allowing user review and adjustment prior to execution. In feedback phase, the user evaluates outcomes against target metrics and submits refinements through the interface. This information is

recorded in the knowledge graph to enable iterative improvement and more informed decisions in subsequent experiments.

3.1.1 Markov Decision Process

MDP is a mathematical framework for sequential decision-making under uncertainty. It models an environment as states S and actions A , with transition probabilities P that map a current state and chosen action to a distribution over next states, and a reward function R that scores outcomes. Under the Markov property, the next state depends only on the current state and action. The objective is to compute a policy that maximizes expected cumulative reward, typically discounted by a factor γ .

The background motivation and the initial concept design of the probabilistic decision model used in ExtremeXP's Options Explorer are described in deliverable D2.1.

The MDP models an optimal strategy for data analysis under user limitations and preferences. This stochastic process is comprised of three sets of states:

1. the initial state $DATA$ when user specifies the context (intent, dataset, hard and soft constraints),
2. set of possible algorithms $ALG_1, ALG_2, \dots, ALG_n$ that match the $DATA$ state,
3. set of models $MODEL_{i,j}$, $1 \leq j \leq k_i$ for algorithm ALG_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$.

At the beginning in the state $DATA$, the algorithm is chosen with the probability p_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$. Suitable action in this step represents the selection of an algorithm. In the state ALG_i , the model $MODEL_{i,j}$ is chosen with the probability $p_{i,j}$. Suitable action in this step represents the selection of the model. Figure 4 represents the general graph of the MDP.

Each state receives a reward for fulfilling the soft constraint, where the reward can be any positive number greater than 1. We will denote with $r(s)$ the sum of all rewards for the state s . The utility function quantifies the optimality of states by assigning them the utility value associated with being in that state. The utility of a state s is equal to

$$u(s) = r(s) + \gamma \max_{a \in A} \sum_{s' \in S} p_{s,s'}^a u(s'),$$

where γ , $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$, is a discount factor, A is an action space and $p_{s,s'}^a$ is a transition probability of moving from a state s to s' made due to an action a .

The utility of each path of the MDP model, from the beginning state $DATA$ to an algorithm ALG_i and to the model $MODEL_{i,j}$ is calculated as a sum of utilities of path states

$$u(PATH_i) = u(DATA) + u(ALG_i) + u(MODEL_{i,j}),$$

$$1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq k_i.$$

The utilities of the paths are ranked, with the optimal path having the greatest utility. The user is shown the list of the first three paths.

The user provides information about the context during the initial setup of the MDP, which guides the process of finding the optimal strategy. Over time, MDP evolves with information gathered from the users (usage frequency and feedback). Each subsequent version of MDP improves the previous one by incorporating additional information and further adapting to the user's needs.

Figure 4: General model of the Markov decision process

3.1.2 Semantic Model for Probabilistic Reasoning

The semantic model (see Figure 5) represents a probabilistic, experiment-centric knowledge base that supports the Options Explorer for complex analytics workflows. It integrates a domain and experiment layer with a decision layer based on MDPs, grounded in the formal language of decision options [MKT+24]. All information about datasets, algorithms, models, users, intents, and constraints is encoded as a knowledge graph; the MDPs operate over this graph to rank alternatives and recommend optimal workflows. Figure 6 provides schema for this layer, showing how these conceptual elements are implemented as classes and associations in the Options Explorer.

At the core of the schema are entities describing experiments and analytical assets. Class Dataset represents concrete data collections, annotated with their domain context, such as *machine_milling* and *machine_grinding*, and with metadata relevant for constraints and model selection. Class Algorithm captures abstract method families such as *Neural Network*, *Convolutional Neural Network*, *Long Short-Term Memory*, and *Recurrent Neural Network*. Models are concrete trainable artefacts that implement a given Algorithm and are trained or evaluated on particular Datasets; in the graph, each Model node is linked both to its Algorithm node and to the Dataset nodes it uses.

Figure 5 Options Explorer semantic model

Experiments are contextualised by Users, Intents, and domain processes. User instances (e.g., John Smith, Janez Novak) are linked to the experiments and options they selected and can be annotated with an expertise score for later learning. Intent represents high-level analytical goals such as anomaly detection, prediction, or feature extraction; an Intent is associated with one or more Datasets and Models that are suitable for achieving it. Domain entities (e.g., particular manufacturing processes) further specialize the context and connect to Datasets and Intents.

The probabilistic decision layer is represented explicitly through the classes MDP, State, Action, Transition and Reward. In the knowledge graph, a particular decision problem is represented by an individual *MDP_1* connected to a collection of *States_1* and to the associated *Actions_1/Actions_2*, *Transitions_1/Transitions_2*, and *Rewards_1* in the schema.

Operationally, the semantic model supports a multi-step decision process. The user first selects a domain and Intent and specifies hard and soft constraints. Hard constraints are applied as logical filters over the knowledge graph, yielding subgraphs of Datasets, Algorithms and Models that are structurally compatible and respect all non-negotiable limits. For each of the three decision dimensions (dataset, algorithm, model), an MDP is instantiated or reused over the filtered States; its Reward function is parameterized by the soft constraints. Solving these MDPs yields an optimal policy and associated utilities, which are used to produce a ranked list of recommended options, for example, “optimal algorithm and model for the given dataset under specified requirements” in the manufacturing use case. The resulting model is modular, separating context, assets, and decision processes.

Figure 6: Entity-relationship diagram of the Options Explorer's semantic model

3.2 Evolution of the MDP decisions

3.2.1 Initial MDP decision-making

In the beginning, for the specific dataset and the intent, there are N different experiments, where each combination of the algorithm and the model ($ALG_i, MODEL_{i,j}$) is performed only once. In this situation, the probabilities of selecting an algorithm are equal,

$$p_i = \frac{1}{n}, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

and it is equally likely to choose any model (child) of an algorithm

$$p_{i,j} = \frac{1}{k_i}, 1 \leq j \leq k_i.$$

Example 1. UC5 partner organization collects and analyses high-frequency grinding machine sensor data to detect machine anomalies. Their intent can be described as *Identify mechanical and electrical components' anomalies of a grinding machine, or shortened, anomaly detection* with the general method of analysis *multiclass classification*. They considered the following algorithms or classifier types: neural network (NN), convolutional neural network (CNN), and recurrent neural network (RNN). The hard constraints are the intent, general method, and memory of at most 16 GB RAM. Figure 7 represents the graph of the Markov decision process for the UC5 anomaly data.

Figure 7: Initial MDP model for UC5 data

The soft constraints are: (1) Accuracy of at least 0.9, (2) Precision of at least 0.9, (3) Recall of at least 0.8, (4) F1 score of at least 0.85, and (5) The processing unit (PU) is GPU. The state receives the reward of 10 for fulfilling each soft constraint and 0 otherwise. The user is shown the first three ranked MDP paths that include the values of variables chosen for the soft constraints.

Table 1 The best three options proposed by MDP for UC5 ranked by their utility value

Rank	Path	Utility value	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	PU
1	DATA-CNN-CNN6	768.43	0.9696	0.9709	0.9684	0.9692	GPU
2	DATA-CNN-CNN2	568.45	0.8586	0.8662	0.8571	0.8568	GPU

3	DATA-CNN-CNN4	468.46	0.8283	0.8442	0.8263	0.8228	GPU
---	---------------	--------	--------	--------	--------	--------	-----

3.2.2 Initial MDP with the ranking of the soft constraints

Frequently, the soft constraints are not of the same importance to the user, which results in different rewards for fulfilling them. The user provides the ranked list of M soft constraints, from the most important to the least important one. We will denote with $R(c)$ the rank of the soft constraint c . The reward of the state s for the soft constraint c is then calculated as:

$$r_c(s) = 10(M - R(c) + 1).$$

The cumulative reward of the state s is then equal to $r(s) = \sum_{c=1}^M r_c(s)$.

Example 1 (continued). The user provided the following ranked list of soft constraints: 1. Accuracy of at least 0.9, 2. Recall of at least 0.8, 3. Precision of at least 0.9, 4. F1 score of at least 0.85, and 5. The processing unit (PU) is GPU. Table 2 displays the new results, highlighting even more of the differences between the MDP paths.

Table 2 The best three options proposed by the MDP for UC5 with included ranking of the soft constraints

Rank	Path	Utility value	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	PU
1	DATA-CNN-CNN6	2198.94	0.9696	0.9709	0.9684	0.9692	GPU
2	DATA-CNN-CNN2	1398.97	0.8586	0.8662	0.8571	0.8568	GPU
3	DATA-CNN-CNN4	1198.97	0.8283	0.8442	0.8263	0.8228	GPU

3.2.3 MDP decision-making with prior usage information and feedback

Once the selections of paths in the Markov decision process are recorded, enabling the calculation of new transition probabilities based on the usage frequencies of algorithms and models. We will denote with $f_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ usage frequency of the algorithm ALG_i and with $f_{i,j}, 1 \leq j \leq k_i$ usage frequency of the model $MODEL_{i,j}$. Then the probability of selecting an algorithm ALG_i is calculated with

$$\hat{p}_i = \frac{f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i}$$

The probability of selecting the model $MODEL_{i,j}$ is calculated with

$$\hat{p}_{i,j} = \frac{f_{i,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^{k_i} f_{i,j}}, 1 \leq i \leq n.$$

Example 1 (continued). We simulated usage frequencies for each of the paths of MDP. A graph of the updated MDP is presented in Figure 8. Table 3 displays the results of the MDP with updated transition probabilities.

Table 3 The best three options proposed by the MDP for UC5 with included ranking of the soft constraints and updated transition probabilities

Rank	Path	Utility value	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	PU
1	DATA-CNN-CNN6	3763.03	0.9696	0.9709	0.9684	0.9692	GPU

2	DATA-CNN-CNN2	2963.05	0.8586	0.8662	0.8571	0.8568	GPU
3	DATA-CNN-CNN4	2763.06	0.8283	0.8442	0.8263	0.8228	GPU

Figure 8: MDP model based on prior usage data for UC5

After selecting the optimal option and performing the experiment, user feedback is collected as a measure of his/her assessment of the results. Feedback for the experiment, averaged across all the users who rated it, can be used as an additional hard constraint.

Example 1 (continued). Users rate the experiment results on a scale of 1-10, with 1 being unsatisfactory and 10 being excellent. The new user chooses to add *additional hard constraint Average feedback for the experiment should be at least 8*. The results of the MDP that considers updated hard constraints, ranking of soft constraints, and updated transition probabilities are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 The best three options proposed by the MDP for UC5 with included ranking of the soft constraints, updated transition probabilities and user feedback as a hard constraint

Rank	Path	Utility value	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	PU
1	DATA-CNN-CNN6	3907.23	0.9696	0.9709	0.9684	0.9692	GPU

2	DATA-CNN-CNN2	3107.26	0.8586	0.8662	0.8571	0.8568	GPU
3	DATA-CNN-CNN4	2907.26	0.8283	0.8442	0.8263	0.8228	GPU

3.3 Probabilistic Options Explorer’s implementation details

The Options Explorer is delivered as a Python-based microservice and protected through the Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) system, ensuring secure handling of sensitive experimental data. It provides APIs for defining and managing an experiment’s exploration space, integrating required datasets, identifying optimal parameter configurations, and capturing user feedback. This component is a core utility within ExtremeXP, enabling researchers to articulate experiments, examine their variability points, and evaluate the most effective configurations supported by the framework.

Table 5: Endpoints of Options Explorer service

Method	Path	Summary	Implementation Description
POST	/experiment/add_experiment	Add Experiment	Receives the experiment specification (likely the DSL code or configuration). The implementation parses the input, validates the structure, creates a new record in the experiment database, and assigns a unique ID.
POST	/experiment/add-dataset	Add Experiment Dataset	Integrates a specific dataset source or type into the current experiment context.
GET	/experiment/get_experiment	Get Experiment	Retrieves detailed information for a specific experiment. The experiment_id is passed as a query parameter. If the experiment is found, its details are returned in the response. If the experiment cannot be found, a 404 Not Found error is returned. The request must include a valid JWT access token in the Authorization header.
POST	/experiment/add_experiment_description_type	Add Experiment Description Type	This endpoint allows authenticated users to add a new experiment description type. Users must provide the name, type, and reward for the description type. The request should be sent using form-data. The name represents the type of description, type represents the description's format (e.g., numerical, text), and reward represents the associated reward or importance level for the description. A successful addition returns a success response, while an unauthorized request results in a 401 error.
GET	/experiment/get_experiment_description_types	Get Experiment Description Types	This endpoint allows authenticated users to retrieve all available experiment description types. The response includes a list of all description types, including their names, types, rewards, and description type IDs. If no description types are found or the user is

			not authenticated, an error response will be returned.
POST	/experiment/call_mdp	Call MDP	This endpoint accepts constraints related to experiments, filters experiences based on the provided criteria, and triggers the execution of a Markov Decision Process.
GET	/experiment/select_experiment	Select Experiment	Select an experiment by its ID and log the user's selection in the search history.
POST	/experiment/get_selected_experiments	Get Selected Experiments	Retrieves the list of experiments currently marked as active or selected by the user.
POST	/experiment/add_user_feedback	Add User Feedback	Captures user input or evaluation results regarding an experiment's performance, usability, or correctness. This data is critical for system refinement, often stored in a dedicated feedback database linked to the experiment ID.

3.4 Options Explorer utilization in ExtremeXP use cases

The previous sections provided a detailed discussion of the Options Explorer use in UC5 and its implementation. This section describes the use of the Options Explorer in the other use cases.

UC1 partner organization wants to replace the physical model for the prediction of flash floods with the AI model. Their intent can be described as flood prediction, with a deep learning model as a general method of analysis. They considered the convolutional neural network (CNN) as an algorithm. The hard constraints are the intent, general method, and processing unit of GPU. The soft constraints are: (1) Accuracy of at least 0.9, (2) Precision of at least 0.9, (3) Recall of at least 0.75, (4) Mean square error (MSE) of at most 0.03, and (5) Inference time of at most 1 second, in that order of importance. The results for the baseline MDP model with the ranking of the soft constraints are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 The best options proposed by the MDP for UC1 with included ranking of the soft constraints

Rank	Path	Utility value	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	MSE	Inference time
1	DATA-CNN-CNN ₁	2638.88	0.96	0.83	0.77	0.0276	0.5
2	DATA-CNN-CNN ₄	2538.89	0.97	0.73	0.84	0.0202	1.3
3	DATA-CNN-CNN ₂	2438.89	0.95	0.76	0.79	0.0376	0.5

UC2 partner organization is searching for an optimal machine learning model for cyber threats detection. Their intent can be described as Cyber threats detection with the general method of analysis binary classification. They considered the XGBoost machine learning algorithm. The hard constraints are the intent and general method. The soft constraints are: (1) Recall of at least 0.9, (2) Precision of at least 0.9, (3) F1 score of at least 0.9, (4) Accuracy of at least 0.85, in that order of importance. The results for the baseline MDP model with the ranking of the soft constraints are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 7 The best three options proposed by the MDP for UC2 with included ranking of the soft constraints

Rank	Path	Utility value	Recall	Precision	F1 score	Accuracy
1	DATA-XGBoost- XGBoost6	1702.91	0.94	0.9058	0.9226	0.87
2	DATA- XGBoost - XGBoost7	1302.93	0.959	0.8561	0.9046	0.8332
2	DATA- XGBoost - XGBoost8	1302.93	0.928	0.8779	0.9025	0.8345

3.5 Options Explorer Graphical interface

To facilitate use of the Options Explorer, a dedicated graphical user interface has been developed that allows users to define their requirements in an intuitive manner and, in return, receive a ranked list of optimal options. Figure: 9 shows the interface for defining an experiment and its associated constraints. Figure: 10 shows the interface that presents the results of the decision making performed by the Options Explorer.

Figure: 9 Options Explorer: Definition of intent, constraints, and operating conditions

Figure: 10 Options Explorer: Ranked options in accordance with the defined context

4 Traceability and Trustworthiness for Experiment-driven Analytics

4.1 Context-Aware Access Control

4.1.1 Overview

The main objective of context-aware access control is to provide a mechanism for protecting resources on the ExtremeXP framework. In real settings, data analysts and data engineers involved in data-driven experimentations, along with data owners/providers participating, may be quite dispersed, coming from different administrative domains. Therefore, it is important to avoid single-domain and centralized solutions but offer a flexible and transparent access control mechanism that is able to enforce and cope with context-aware authorization policies. Thus, ExtremeXP approach allows data analysts and data engineers to execute their experiments and workflows securely, accessing only the resources they are permitted to, through a fine-grained Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) implemented on a blockchain, thereby enhancing trustworthiness and transparency. To comply with that definition, this section presents the results of implementing the ExtremeXP Access Control mechanism.

To evaluate the mechanism, this section introduces the outcomes of using Smart Contracts in the Hyperledger Besu blockchain framework for controlling access, by taking the user's contextual attributes into account (KPI-6.1). Also, based on KPI-6.2, all possible use-case combinations were tested, and a performance assessment was conducted to demonstrate the transaction-time overhead required to comply with KPI-6.3.

In addition, use cases were evaluated through simulated scenarios featuring various contextual attributes to assess the behaviour of the access control mechanism and its feasibility for application on the ExtremeXP. Additionally, this work includes a practical demonstration of the mechanism, which effectively protects data from unauthorized access and evaluates access requests based on contextual attributes.

4.1.2 Architecture and Components

The Access control architecture comprises three main components: the first two are the off-chain components, namely the Access Control Interface (ACI) and the Access Control Proxy (AC Proxy). The AC Proxy integrates with the Execution Engine (EE) and the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) to protect data processing execution. The third module is the institutional node, which comprises a Keycloak and a blockchain node. Each data controller has its own Keycloak instance integrated with the off-chain components to issue JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) and provide identity management. The blockchain has a set of deployed smart contracts to enforce rules based on the ABAC standard. Table 8 presents the components of the decentralized access control.

Table 8: Access Control components description

Component	Description
AC Proxy	An off-chain component that intercepts the user's request and redirects it to be evaluated before reaching backend modules.
Access Control Interface	Component responsible for registering users, policies, retrieving user attributes, and delivering JWT tokens for user authentication.
Keycloak	Identity Manager, which stores institutional user data and interacts with the Access Control Interface.
Execution Engine	Processes data for a task.
Blockchain	A distributed ledger that provides transparency and traceability to smart contract execution.
Smart Contracts	Auto-executed code which enforces policies to protect resource access.
Resource ID	Identifier of the resource.

Requirements and Assumptions

As a requirement for access control usage, the user must be registered through the authentication flow. The user must be a company staff member of one of the ExtremeXP members. Furthermore, the user can be a third-party partner of an ExtremeXP member. The data controller must define a rule for the resource, and the access control mechanism only protects the data that has previously defined rules. While resources that do not have defined rules, the access control mechanism grants access automatically. Another requirement is that all connections between the request, the access control mechanism, and between the access control and other mechanisms should be made through the HTTPS protocol to ensure that all data is exchanged cryptographically.

We assume that all data is secure in the DDM, and the data processing is made only within the secure Execution Engine (EE). Moreover, the processing occurs only when the AC Proxy receives the result of the evaluation request from the blockchain. All requests must go through the AC Proxy.

In addition, the AC Proxy is location-agnostic. Since the access control policy is stored on the blockchain, the AC Proxy location or its redundancy does not impact its function. This feature enhances the system's fault tolerance, as multiple instances can connect to redundant Keycloak instances.

4.1.2.1 Authentication Flow

The Access Control Interface manages user authentication, user registration, and the deployment of new policies. It also bridges users from the Web2 application to the Web3 environment. The ACI consists of three layers: a REST API for integration, User Management, and a Blockchain interface.

Through its integration with the Frontend App and Keycloak, it is possible to register and authenticate users, retrieve user data, and assign attributes to them. Upon registration, user information is stored in the organization’s Keycloak, and authenticated users receive a JSON Web Token (JWT) issued by Keycloak. The blockchain does not store users’ credentials or Personally Identifiable Information (PII). Instead, only a user’s wallet address is maintained on-chain, while user attributes are maintained off-chain in the institutional Keycloak database.

The authentication flow involves a series of straightforward steps (Figure 10). Initially, the user logs in (step 1) via the system Frontend App. In the next step, the Access Control Interface authenticates the user against the organization’s Keycloak system (step 2). If the user is registered and the provided credentials are valid, the organization’s Keycloak issues a JWT as an access token (step 2). Finally, this JWT token is securely delivered to the user through the Frontend App.

Figure 11: Access control architecture

If a user is not registered, they must be registered by following the steps described previously through the ACI. However, details are presented in Figure 11. In this flow, the user requests registration (step 1). The ACI redirects the user's address to the Keycloak of the institution that the user belongs to (step 2). Moreover, the ACI creates the user's wallet (step 3), and this wallet is bound with the user data by the Keycloak (step 4). Then, the ACI returns the wallet address, user information, and wallet key to the user, and the user registers their wallet on Metamask³ (step 5). Finally, the user signs a transaction on the blockchain, allowing Keycloak to request the blockchain on behalf of the user (step 6). The blockchain returns to the user confirmation that the transaction has been registered on the ledger (step 7).

³ <https://metamask.io/>

Figure 12: On-Behalf action flow

4.1.2.2 Authorisation Flow

In Figure 10, the diagram illustrates the process of granting or denying access to a resource. The user must have a valid JWT token obtained from the authentication flow. The steps start with the user requesting a resource, which is intercepted by the AC Proxy (step 3). The AC Proxy checks whether the requested Resource ID, which refers to the resource's unique identifier, has an associated access control policy. If so, it forwards the user request to Keycloak, along with the resource hash, which serves as the identifier on the DDM (step 4). Then, Keycloak writes a transaction based on the request information, adding any necessary context attributes for evaluation against the access control policies defined in smart contracts (step 5). A series of smart contracts evaluates the policies and generates an event that contains the result once the transaction is complete. Therefore, the smart contract emits it, and Keycloak catches that result. It sends the results, Permit or Deny, to AC Proxy (step 6). In the next step, AC Proxy provides the user's UUID, Resource ID, and a token with the necessary permission for EE to access DDM (step 7). EE requests access to the resource, and this access request is routed through the AC Proxy because EE and DDM do not have a direct connection (step 8). The AC Proxy forwards the EE request to the DDM (step 9).

Then, DDM provides access (step 10), and the AC Proxy returns the resource with access to the user (step 11). This component assumes that all data is secure in the DDM, and the data processing is made only within the secure EE. Moreover, the processing occurs only when the AC Proxy receives the result of the evaluation request from the blockchain. Additionally, the AC Proxy is location-agnostic; since the access control policy is stored on the blockchain, the AC Proxy's location or redundancy does not impact its function. This feature enhances the system's fault tolerance, as multiple instances can connect to redundant Keycloak instances.

4.1.2.3 Policy Smart Contracts

The authorisation flow presented in Figure 10 does not provide details about how policy is enforced in blockchain and how smart contracts work together to grant or deny access. It is a flow that occurs under the on-chain component, which we describe below.

The design structures the smart contracts in policy points, as shown in Figure 12. The set of policy points smart contracts includes the Policy Decision Point (PDPSC), Policy Administration Point (PAPSC), and Policy Information Point (PIPSC), following the XACML standard. Furthermore, there is a dedicated RulesContract per use case. The smart contracts act together to decide whether to permit or deny

access to a resource and return the result to the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP). In this scenario, the PEP is composed of Keycloak and the AC Proxy. The resource contains a URI, which serves both as the means of accessing the resource and as its unique identifier, commonly referred to as the ResourceID. This identifier requires protection, and access to the resource should be granted exclusively when permitted by a defined set of policies. Once the request reaches the PEP (step 1), the user waits for the enforcement decision, and the PEP sends the request to the blockchain for evaluation (step 2). Inside the blockchain, the request is sent to the PDPSC, which gets from PAPSC the RulesContract address that protects the resource related to the request (step 3). PAPSC has a mapping of all the protected Resource IDs associated with their respective Rule Contracts' addresses. Then, PDPSC requests the contextual attributes related to the user address and the resource ID from PIPSC (step 4). Following this, PIPSC verifies whether the user has a relation to the resource. Otherwise, it is enough for the evaluation to deny access to the resource.

After that, PDPSC makes a delegate call to the RulesContract to evaluate the rules (step 5). The RulesContract has the logical operation of rules tailored to each use case. The contract receives data from the request and the PIPSC. It evaluates access based on the rules in the policy defined for that ResourceID. Thus, the RulesContracts sends the result to the PDPSC. Finally, the PDPSC emits the decision event as a transaction on a valid block (step 6). Then PEP reads it and returns the decision to the AC Proxy (step 7). Finally, the PEP emits the result to the user (step 8).

Figure 13: Smart contracts evaluation request flow

4.1.2.4 Policy Translator

Following the mapped use cases detailed in section 4.1.5, the ExtremeXP Access Control takes leverage of the predictability of rules to enhance new policy development and deployment. With the Policy Translator Submodule in the ACI, the users of the ExtremeXP framework can create new policies to protect resources and support new use cases on their own. Figure 13 presents the Access Control Interface's internal modules, with the Policy Translator Submodule shown in the green box.

Figure 14: Access Control Interface module with the submodules for resource protection and policy translation features. The figure represents the basic flow for the deployment of a JSON Policy.

For correct policy translation, the Policy Translator Submodule comprises four internal components that share responsibility for translating the input set of rules into a Solidity policy. The first component is the Rules Validator, which verifies that the input JSON complies with all the definitions required to translate into a Solidity policy. This component serves as a guarantee that from that point forward, the input can be trusted to have a successful translation. This component executes first in the translation pipeline after the request reaches the REST API.

After input validation, the data is ready to begin policy assembly. For that, the Structure Builder receives the validated data and starts interpreting each rule block. It is essential to note that the policy in JSON format already includes the specific rule name. With that name, the Structure Builder consults the Rules Catalogue to obtain a structured reference to that rule. With the structured rule, the Structure Builder can identify the attributes associated with that rule and add them to an area reserved for the policy's expected values. It is also the Structure Builder's responsibility to identify and track the logical connectives between rules.

Once the mapped data from the input JSON is transformed into structured rules within the Structure Builder, the Solidity Policy Builder consolidates all the information into a single text file to generate a Solidity script. After the script is finalized, the policy is sent to the Blockchain Interface submodule for deployment and registration on the blockchain. If the operation is successful, the REST API returns an HTTP 201 response code along with the policy address in the response body.

4.1.3 User Roles

Based on the GDPR and what was previously defined in D2.1 [AAB+24], we have the following roles in the system.

- **Data controller:** defines and deploys access and usage control policies on the blockchain. These policies are enforced through smart contracts.
- **Data processor:** processes the data on behalf of the data controller. The Data Processor requests access to data stored in data management.
- **Supervisor authority:** Checks compliance with defined policies through logs.
- **Data subject:** A person whose data is being processed and can be identified. According to the GDPR, their data must be protected, and their privacy is preserved.

4.1.4 Attribute-Based Access Control Rules and KPI-6.1

To protect the policies, we have designed a set of rules for each use case. We are following the ABAC standard for it. First, a table of common rules applicable to all use cases was created (Table 9), which presents contextual attributes (R1, R2). Furthermore, we present tables with contextual attributes suitable for each use case. Tables help map the rules suitable for each use case and plan how to create the ABAC policies in the format of smart contracts.

To define rules, it is first necessary to determine the attributes that can be used before the rules. Table 9 presents the attributes. We have attributes related to the user, the environment, and the resource. This approach to defining attributes belonging to different owners and origins matches the ABAC definitions, which is helpful for having more fine-grained access control policies. Some attributes come in the request to grant or deny access to the resource; some other attributes come from different system components. A request is composed of a set of data provided through JSON format by the user.

Table 9: List of attributes, definitions, belongings, and where they come from

ATTRIBUTE	DEFINITION	BELONGS TO	Origin
UserID	User identification	User	Request
Location	User location	User	Request
IP	User IP address	User	Request
Hour	Hour of the request	Environment	Keycloak
Day	Request day of week	Environment	Keycloak
ResourceHash	Resource's requested content hash	Resource	DDM
Role	User's Role	User	Keycloak

Using the XACML standard, we have defined rules that compose the access control policies for the Use Cases (UCs). Table 10 presents these rules and the attributes used in the evaluation. Moreover, the table shows the origin of the data necessary for the evaluation. The user request provides the data for rules R1, R2, and R3. Those rules are captured by the AC Proxy when the request arrives. In contrast, the rules R3 and R5 data is provided by Keycloak, which is the better approach, mainly to protect the data of these rules from being faked.

The contextual attributes are helpful in refining access control for use cases through rules that evaluate the attributes of a user and a resource based on the request. For the use cases, there are contextual attributes present in all UCs, such as geolocation (R1), IP address (R2), and specific day of the week (R5), as shown in Table 9. After we have defined the attributes, we have defined the rules based on those attributes to protect the resource in the requests. Table 10 lists all the rules for the use cases, some of them have contextual attributes, such as R1, R2, and R5. These contextual attributes help to apply fine-grained access control and achieve KPI-6.2. Moreover, Table 10 presents the rules, along with their descriptions and logical representations, which are important for enforcing the rule definition in the blockchain.

Table 10: List of all rules defined for the use cases' policies

Rule	Description	Logical Representation
R1	User sends a request from a location inside authorized location	Location ∈ Premises
R2	User's IP gathered by the AC Proxy in the request	IP_Address ∈ Whitelist

R3	User must have a role with access permission to the resource	User_Role ∈ Allowed_Roles
R4	The request should be made using HTTPS protocol	Protocol("HTTPS") = True
R5	The request should be made within weekdays	IS_WEEKDAY(Day) = True
R6	The request should be made within timeshift	8 ≤ Hour ≤ 17
R7	The hash of the resource is equal to registered in smart contract	ResourceHASH(Resource)=ExpectedHash

With the rules defined, it is possible to map which rules are used for each use case in ExtremeXP. Table 11 shows the rules applied for each use case. The column Policy shows the concatenation of a set of rules that compose a policy for each use case. The column Policy indicates that the use case policies employ different rules to match the specific needs of each use case.

Table 11: Table 3. Rule per use case to compose the policy

Use case	Policy
UC1	R1 ^ R2 ^ R3 ^ R4 ^ R7 ^ R8
UC2	R1 ^ R2 ^ R3 ^ R4 ^ R5 ^ R6 ^ R7 ^ R8
UC3	R1 ^ R2 ^ R3 ^ R4 ^ R5 ^ R6 ^ R7
UC4	R1 ^ R2 ^ R3 ^ R4 ^ R5 ^ R6 ^ R7
UC5	R1 ^ R2 ^ R3 ^ R4 ^ R5 ^ R6 ^ R7 ^ R8

When a user requests a resource, it undergoes a web request that includes specific attributes, as presented in Table 9. In the request's body, some of the attributes are provided, such as the resource and the IP. Moreover, through the session token, it is possible to identify the user and bind their information with what is stored in the Identity Management (Keycloak). A request is composed of a set of information provided by the user when asked to access a resource. That information includes the resource and the user's IP address. An example of a request is presented below.

```
{
  "uri": "/resource_1",
  "origin_ip": "172.21.0.1",
  "scope": "read:data"
},
```

Listing 3: Example of a request

4.1.5 Use cases and KPI-6.2

UC1

The first use case is about flood and disaster prediction. This use case involves sharing end-user data to improve the models. Then, the end-user data must be protected and anonymized. Moreover, end-users may have access to the training model result as well as the CS personnel. Jointly with the rules presented in Table 9, we defined some contextual attributes for the use case, which refine the access to the data in this use case. CS personnel access is granted according to the role presented in Rules CA4, CA5, and CA6. Finally, there is a hash verification to protect access to the resource.

UC2

The second use case involves detecting attacks on the systems and predicting the attacking behaviour. There is a data hash verification rule and a threshold of hash signatures that enable I2CAT third parties to have access to the resource. The third party also only has access when it proves that it has a partnership with I2CAT.

UC3

Regarding the third-party use case, the rules were defined to address the challenge of sharing data between Airbus and public-sector bodies (e.g. police departments). As there is a partnership between Airbus and the public sector, access to the data is provided only through the hash of the agreement, allowing third parties to have access to the data.

UC4

The table related to the UC4 presents rules related to the training model and data sharing for mobility. Then, Moby personnel and end-users can access the data. The rules from one to seven are similar to those presented in previous use cases (e.g., UC1 to UC3). As there are concerns regarding data integrity, we have defined a rule to verify data integrity on rule eight. Moreover, as the user may have access to sensitive data, rule nine verifies whether the end-user should have access, mainly because it involves sensitive data related to the end-user geolocation.

UC5

Use case five, like the other use cases. However, there are more rules to protect the dataset and workflows in Rules CA1 to CA3. Those rules regarding workflow and dataset are important because, in this use case, data sharing related to predictive maintenance occurs between machine owners. Then, it is important to protect sensitive data from the machine sensor.

4.1.6 Access Control Experimental Results and KPI-6.3

To evaluate the access control mechanism implemented for ExtremeXP, we have designed scenarios to assess the enforcement of rules and the performance of the decentralized mechanism, which grants or denies access through smart contracts. Table 12 presents scenarios to evaluate each rule. In scenarios from 1 to 7, a request is made passing all valid data in the request, except for one of the scenario descriptions, to validate whether the policy will have the expected behaviour. This behaviour is described in the outcome column of Table 12. Furthermore, in scenario 8, we have composed a request that provides all the necessary data to grant access to a resource.

Table 12: Experimental Scenarios and rules applied with respective outcomes

Scenario	Description	Rules								Outcome
		R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	
Scenario1	On-Behalf not authorized	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Deny Access
Scenario2	User without authorised IP	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Deny Access
Scenario3	User group is not allowed	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Deny Access

Scenario4	User Role is not allowed	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	Deny Access
Scenario5	Request is out time shift	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	Deny Access
Scenario6	Hash is not	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	Deny Access
Scenario7	User is out of authorized Geolocation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	Deny Access
Scenario8	Grant Access	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Grant Access

To assess this KPI, we implemented the same policy used in ExtremeXP Access Control (ExtremeXP AC) within Solidity smart contracts. The policy was translated into a JavaScript Keycloak policy with minor adaptations to comply with Keycloak ABAC policy format.

For evaluation, the use case outlined in the KPI 6-2 table was executed 1,000 times, with each execution separated by 30 consecutive rounds. Figure 15 presents the results of the experiment with a 95% confidence interval. The figure illustrates the response time of each platform tested. As expected, the centralized Keycloak ABAC implementation typically has lower response times than the ExtremeXP AC. The ExtremeXP AC had an average transaction response time of 14ms, demonstrating consistent behaviour across consecutive rounds, resulting in predictable variation. The Keycloak ABAC platform had an average transaction response time of 12ms, but, unlike the ExtremeXP AC, its behaviour is less predictable, with greater variation across rounds.

Although the variation is higher, the centralized approach of the Keycloak ABAC platform for controlling access avoids the time spent on node communication, ordering, and validation that a decentralized approach, such as the ExtremeXP AC, requires. Nonetheless, the ExtremeXP AC exhibits predictable, stable behaviour, increasing by only 2ms per transaction, resulting in an average overhead of 14.29%. **Considering the limit of the confidence interval of 95% of the results for Keycloak ABAC (12.14ms \mp 0.89ms) and the ExtremeXP AC (14.59ms \mp 0.1ms), we have that the average overhead is 10.07%.** It is important to highlight that there are cases where the ExtremeXP AC achieved a lower time per transaction than the centralized baseline.

Figure 15: Experiment of 30 rounds with 1000 requests, presenting the variation over time of the Time per Transaction metric of the tested mechanisms, the ExtremeXP Access Control, and the Keycloak ABAC.

4.2 Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based dataset provenance mechanism

4.2.1 Overview

As part of Task 2.3, we have designed and developed a Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based dataset provenance mechanism. It provides the means to attach metadata to any datasets managed by the Decentralized Data Management system (DDM), in a transparent, immutable, and unique manner, using blockchain technologies. This mechanism introduces a novel approach in characterizing datasets, based on a wide range of metadata that are important for inferring the input data quality, used in ExtremeXP-based experiments (e.g., unbiased, adequate volume, appropriate quality etc.). Such metadata are appended to DDM-managed datasets requests, in an immutable manner, engaging trustworthy expert human evaluators or third-party services that can automatically extract such data aspects. Along these characteristics, information such as dataset owner(s) and parent dataset(s) used, are attached, through minting process (“minting” is the common term for creating a new NFT token), as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) over a permissioned and private blockchain.

The choice of using NFTs for implementing dataset provenance support in ExtremeXP, compared to a classic web2.0 metadata management approaches, was made considering the important advantages of having an immutable, transparent, and safe persistence of the metadata layer that can be trusted by all parties. This is evident, since the process involved is defined in smart contracts and the protocol is implemented by the nodes participating in the blockchain network instead of being dictated by a single server.

Therefore, we have designed and implemented a decentralized prototype application based on smart contracts that define a process for minting a new unique token representing each dataset when specific requirements are met. This involves a specific number of attributes, defined by data engineers, which can be evaluated by multiple authorized entities participating in the blockchain network. These

entities may refer to human or software-based auditors that are able to evaluate datasets aspects to be used for their quality inference against specific user requests for finding certain data artefacts. When the evaluation process is complete, the dataset owner can mint the uniquely identified NFT that immutably characterizes the dataset uploaded to the ExtremeXP platform. All the information associated with this unique object is stored on chain and the whole minting process is transparent to everyone participating in the network. Whenever a transaction, that changes the “state” of the blockchain network, takes place, appropriate messages (events in the “smart-contract” world) are generated and broadcasted among the nodes of the network, so that the corresponding actions regarding the application interaction can be made. In our case, this involves informing the users through a user interface (UI) about the actions made.

During the last period of the project the different prototype implementations of the NFT-based dataset provenance mechanism, converged to a final version that was integrated with DDM. Therefore, this optional mechanism is now released as an integral part of DDM for holistically managing datasets that are used for experiment-driven data analytics tasks in the scope of ExtremeXP platform. Furthermore, we introduced explicit components that demonstrate how software-based aspects can be considered in the dataset metadata management in ExtremeXP with respect to specific user requests for data artefacts that exhibit certain characteristics. Specifically, we used the concept of *Expectations*, for allowing our users to define the minimum quantitative and qualitative aspects that should be exhibited by any dataset required for a specific experiment. These expectations can involve details of the expected structure for the requested dataset (e.g., schema, number of columns, rows expected, specific value types required, etc.). Next, we developed the necessary subcomponents that leverage large language models (LLMs) to consider these user-driven expectations and autofill, where possible, column to reduce significant manual effort. Next, these expectations are being evaluated against any uploaded dataset that could potentially be used in an experiment.

The details of the expectations-based automated evaluation are considered as part of the metadata that are handled by the NFT-based dataset provenance mechanism. Furthermore, metadata produced by the ethical assessment service—derived from DDM-generated dataset metadata—are used to evaluate ethical, legal, and risk-related aspects of a dataset before it is admitted for experimental use. In addition, we have implemented rewarding functionalities for data owners that are able to meet the users’ expectations in an experiment setting. This part also demonstrates a potential monetization path for ExtremeXP technology.

In the following subsections, the final conceptual design of this mechanism is discussed (Section 4.7.2) while technical details on smart contracts (Section 4.7.3) and the grounding work (Section 4.7.4) are presented. Last, we present the interaction workflows (Section 4.7.5) and an illustrative scenario (sections 4.7.6, 4.7.7) that depicts the main meaningful interactions with the capabilities offered by the NFT-based dataset provenance mechanism.

4.2.2 Final conceptual design

Building on the architecture presented in Deliverable D5.1, we extend the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) system by integrating an NFT-based dataset provenance mechanism. This extension relies on smart contracts and supporting pipelines for compilation, deployment, and event handling across different blockchain environments. The core functionality of these smart contracts involves the registration of dataset requests with optional monetization conditions, as well as the registration of datasets submitted by uploaders and validated by registered validators.

As depicted in Figure 16, dataset requesters register requests by defining expectation specifications through the expectation page illustrated in Section 7.3.8.4 of Deliverable 5.1 and attaching IPFS URIs pointing to report generated by Expectation Suite Generation service described in Section 7.3.5 of Deliverable 5.1. Upon request registration, requesters receive a non-fungible token (NFT) that acts as a certificate for the dataset request.

On the other hand, dataset uploaders register datasets using the metadata generation and dataset report generation services, described in Section 7.3.5 of Deliverable 5.1. Validation is conducted by registered validators, including both automated DDM services, such as the Expectation Suite Validation service, and human experts, who submit validation results together with IPFS URIs referencing the corresponding validation reports. If the validation process is successful, uploaders can claim rewards in the form of non-fungible tokens (NFTs) as certificates and, where applicable, fungible tokens as incentives.

All blockchain transactions and corresponding events generated during the whole process act as provenance logs and are replicated in the DDM catalogue services through dedicated task and metadata orchestration pipelines. The details of subcomponents and respective smart contracts are explained in the following section 4.7.3.

Figure 16: NFT-based dataset provenance architecture (non-dashed components) integrated into the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) system.

4.2.3 Smart contracts

We developed a set of modular smart contracts in latest Solidity version (0.8.20) and deployed them on an EVM-compatible public blockchain (Sepolia⁴ Ethereum Network) to support the NFT-base provenance mechanism. We leveraged OpenZeppelin⁵ well established libraries, in particular the access control framework and Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA⁶) cryptographic primitives, to enforce permissions and securely authorize sensitive contract interactions against unauthorized actions, replay attacks and tampering.

The contracts are structured in a manner to support governance-driven functionality, and clear separation of responsibilities. As illustrated in Figure 17, we dedicated different smart contracts for dataset registration, dataset request management, validation management, reward claiming and supporting registries for categories, file formats, and validators.

In the current deployment, the DDM application acts as the governor. However, the architecture is explicitly designed to support more advanced governance models, including multi-governance setups where multiple application signers (governing entities) can coexist under a Governor or Timelock-controlled account.

In the following paragraphs, we briefly describe the role of each contract and how they interact with each other.

Figure 17: On-chain and off-chain actions of the NFT-based dataset provenance mechanism per role

4.2.3.1 *CategoryRegistry and FileFormatRegistry*

The CategoryRegistry and FileFormatRegistry contracts store specific lists which define which dataset categories and file formats, respectively, are accepted and enforce corresponding restrictions whenever interested parties register dataset requests or datasets

Both registries follow the same governance approach described above. The owner role is responsible for administrative actions of the contract, while the application signer role is allowed to add or remove categories and formats during operation (DDM is the application signer role in our deployment). Whenever such a transaction is recorded, a corresponding event is emitted.

4.2.3.2 *DatasetRequestRegistry*

The DatasetRequestRegistry contract allows dataset requesters to register on chain requests for datasets that satisfy specific requirements and optionally lock a monetary bounty using a signature-based flow. A dataset request is created only if it is accompanied by an EIP-712 typed signature issued by an authorized application signer (DDM is the application signer in our deployment). This signed message includes the requester address, expectation suite hash produced by DDM, expected category, file format, and number of datasets, as well as a nonce per requester and expiration time to prevent replay attacks. The contract verifies the signature of this signed message with OpenZeppelin's ECDSA.recover() and only accepts it if the recovered signer matches msg.sender, as expressed in "createDatasetRequestWithSig" method.

During dataset registration, the contract checks that submitted dataset matches the request's declared category and file format, and that it has been successfully validated by the active validators recorded in the ValidationRegistry. If all checks are passed, the owner of submitted dataset is eligible to claim a share of this bounty, given they have not already claimed it. Afterwards, the contract mints a non-transferable NFT to the requester using RewardToken.mint() function imported from RewardToken smart contract. This minted NFT is associated with requester's address and acts as an on-chain unique and immutable certificate representing the dataset request.

Finally, this smart contract also manages (i) the reward distribution for registered datasets, (ii) the automatic closure, once the declared number of registered datasets is reached, and (iii) the refunds of unclaimed funds when the deadline of the request has passed.

4.2.3.3 *DatasetRegistry*

The DatasetRegistry contract allows dataset uploaders to register their uploaded datasets on-chain once they have been processed by the DDM, by providing (i) the dataset URI (IPFS/HTTPS/Zenoh Path), (ii) the hash of the expectation suite (suiteHash) for which they register a dataset, (iii) the file format, and (iv) an optional IPFS URI for the dataset report. To enforce authorization, the contract requires the uploader to sign an off-chain message that includes all these fields plus the uploader address and a per-uploader nonce. Afterwards, the contract verifies the signature with OpenZeppelin's ECDSA.recover() and only accepts it if the recovered signer matches msg.sender. In such a case, the dataset is uniquely and immutably recorded on chain using a deterministic identifier called "fingerprint" and computed as keccak256(abi.encode(uri, suiteHash, msg.sender, nonce)). The fingerprint is used as the unique identifier for the dataset across all other contracts.

4.2.3.4 *ValidatorsRegistry*

The ValidatorsRegistry contract allows the Governor address(es) to manage the authorized entities for submitting validations for registered datasets. Validators consist of automated DDM services (expectation-based validation and ethical assessment are registered in current implementation) as well as human experts. Each validator entry contains a short description and references to off-chain material, using IPFS URIs that point either to code manifests for automated validators or to descriptive documentation for human experts. Actions like validator registration, updates, and removal,

expressed in this contract are governed through OpenZeppelin's AccessControl roles, ensuring that only trusted entities (DDM in particular deployment) can influence dataset validation process.

4.2.3.5 *ValidationRegistry*

The ValidationRegistry contract records validation outcome (successful/not successful) for registered datasets. Authorized validators submit validation results together with cryptographic hashes of the validation results and IPFS URIs pointing to detailed validation report.

The contract offers a function for externally owned accounts to get the validation entries per dataset fingerprint and track whether a dataset has at least three successful validations. This requirement is later used to determine dataset eligibility for rewards and to support transparent provenance auditing. We chose to decouple validations records from dataset registrations so that multiple registrations per dataset fingerprint can take place for multiple available requests.

4.2.3.6 *RewardToken (NFT-based Certificates)*

The RewardToken contract implements a non-transferable (or soulbound) ERC-721 token used to represent certificates and rewards. Distinctive NFTs are issued both to dataset requesters (as proof of request creation) and to dataset uploaders (as certificates of successful dataset registration or validation). In the first case, each minted token contains an IPFS URI pointing to off-chain object and is associated with category, file format, and hash of request, while in the second case it is also associated with hashes of corresponding submitted validations. Transferability can be configured and explicitly disabled for dataset requesters and/or uploaders, ensuring that certificates remain bound to their original owners.

4.2.4 *Technical Grounding*

4.2.4.1 *Smart Contract Tooling and Deployment Pipelines*

Except from smart contracts, which were described in the previous section, we also developed the required asynchronous complex pipelines to handle the compilation, deployment, and event handling of smart contracts during the bootstrap phase as well as the runtime operation. The compilation tasks involved in above pipelines are configurable and read based on the required Solidity version either from the EVM bootstrap parameters or as a runtime argument. The deployment tasks are also configurable and allow for deployment of the smart contracts on any EVM compatible network, defined in similar ways, using the resulting artifacts (ABI and bytecode) extracted from the compilation task. Also, parameters, such as RPC endpoints, chain identifiers, and deployer credentials, are configurable enabling the system to interact with multiple EVM networks through alternative pluggable RPC providers (Infura⁷ used in our case) for contract deployment and transaction submission.

4.2.4.2 *Bootstrap and On-Chain Initialization*

On application startup, a set of asynchronous tasks is executed to support the deployment process. The process begins with constructing and uploading validator-related artifacts to IPFS, covering both automated validation services and human validators. Once IPFS URIs that contain either code manifests for automated validation services, or descriptive metadata for human validators are created, the compiled smart contracts are then deployed by the configured deployer address, followed by a sequence of initialization transactions that establish the initial state of the system. These transactions register the supported file formats and categories, assign the governance role to the DDM, and register the available validators together with references to their associated artifacts. All initialization as well as subsequent transaction receipts, and the events emitted by the corresponding smart contracts are propagated to the DDM catalogue services through appropriate event-handling tasks throughout the system's lifecycle.

4.2.4.3 Runtime Interaction and DDM Integration

Finally, regarding the interaction with the deployed smart contracts, backend services use web3.py library⁸ to programmatically construct, sign and submit transactions as part of automated pipelines, including gas estimation and confirmation tracking. On the frontend, the React-based user interface is integrated with browser wallet support via MetaMask⁹ and uses Web3.js library¹⁰ allowing ExtremeXP users to sign and submit transactions related to dataset request registration, dataset registration, dataset validation, and reward claiming.

4.2.5 Interaction Flow

In this section we will briefly describe the two-core interaction flows for registering a dataset request and registering a dataset for a specific request.

4.2.5.1 Registering a dataset request on chain

As illustrated in the UML diagram of Figure 18, the requester first defines the expected dataset conditions through the “Create Request” page and triggers the generation of an expectation suite by the DDM services. The dedicated UI for this intent, is illustrated in Figures 20, 21 of following section. During this step, the DDM orchestrates specific checks on the request, regarding feasibility, ethical assessment, and validity of the expectation expressions based on requester’s input. Once the checks are passed and expectation suite is created, its hash as well as the associated artifacts (IPFS URIs containing suite definition, documentation, and certificate metadata) are returned to the requester.

The requester then interacts with the DatasetRequestRegistry smart contract and submits the dataset request on chain using the “createDatasetRequestWithSig” method. This method, as described in smart contracts section 4.7.3, is authorized through an EIP-712¹¹ typed signature issued by the DDM application acting as the authorized signer, which is verified on-chain together with nonce and expiration checks. The dedicated interface, in the form of a dialog window, for signing is depicted in Figure 22a of following section. If the signature is verified, the contract validates the requested category and file format against the corresponding registries, locks the provided bounty, and mints a non-transferable NFT that serves as an on-chain immutable certificate in requester’s MetaMask Wallet for this specific dataset request, as depicted in Figure 22b of next section.

Figure 18: UML diagram: Dataset Request Registration.

4.2.5.2 Registering a dataset on chain

The interaction flow for uploading and registering a dataset on chain through DDM system is illustrated in Figure 19. At first, the uploader uses one of the three available mechanisms for file upload presented in Section 7.3.2.2 of Deliverable D5.1 (Standard Upload, Upload from URL or Asynchronous Chunked Upload) and uploads a dataset with the accompanying metadata. Once upload is completed, the appropriate DDM data quality and enrichment services are invoked to generate dataset metadata and a dataset report, store the resulting artifacts on IPFS, and return the corresponding URIs and

identifiers to the uploader. Using these returned artifacts, the uploader signs an off-chain registration message and submits it to the DatasetRegistry contract, which verifies the signature and records the dataset on chain under a deterministic fingerprint. The dedicated interface, in the form of a dialog window, for signing the off-chain registration message is depicted in Figure 23a of following section. If the signature is verified, the contract registers the dataset and emits a corresponding event. This event triggers automated validations from backend services, registered as validators in ValidatorsRegistry contract and also leads to notifications for human validators informing them for pending validation submission. When they submit their validation through the interface, showcased in Figure 23b of following section and given all validations are successful, the uploader can claim their rewards through the last dialog interface used and depicted in Figure 24 of following section. As a last step, the smart contract mints a non-transferable NFT to the uploader and emits the corresponding on-chain reward event.

Figure 19 : UML diagram: Dataset Registration.

4.2.6 Illustrative scenario

In the next section, we demonstrate the user experience for dataset requesters and dataset uploaders through an illustrative scenario that covers the core interaction flows described in previous section.

4.2.6.1 Creating and Registering Dataset Request

Dataset requesters follow a four-step process to create and register a dataset request on chain. At first, they describe their request and declare specific desired file formats and sectors. Then they upload a sample file of desired dataset to specify mostly schema and parsing parameters such as delimiters. When the upload is successful, the requesters define the specific conditions requested that datasets must satisfy and expressed as expectations, both at the dataset level (e.g., volume constraints, schema structure) and at the column level. This is achieved by selecting validation rules per category (uniqueness, validity, numeric, schema, completeness) and per attribute. Wherever possible, default values are auto-filled, and column descriptions are generated by the DDM’s LLM-based enrichment services, reducing significant manual effort, as depicted in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Frontend: Dataset Request Creation-Defining Expectations.

When all conditions are defined, the requester can persist the expectation suite and can register the dataset request on chain. At this point, the DDM backend services generate a structured dataset request report (enriched with LLM-based descriptions, expectation summaries, argument values, visual graphs, and documentation links, as depicted in figure 21), upload the resulting artifacts to IPFS, return the corresponding URIs and suite hash to the requester. As a final step of this scenario, the requester adds the bounty and expiration date, signs the request via an EIP-712 flow, and receives the non-transferable NFT certificate in MetaMask wallet, upon successful registration. This final step is illustrated in Figures 22a and 22b.

Figure 21: Frontend: Expectations Report for Dataset Requests

Figure 22: a) Registering Dataset Request, b) Receiving Dataset Request NFT in MetaMask Wallet

4.2.6.2 Uploading and Registering Dataset Request

In the next scenario we will illustrate the user experience regarding the dataset registration flow as described in previous section. The dialog (Figure 23a) guides the uploader to either select an already

existing IPFS URI, where the dataset is stored or to trigger a backend upload. Upon uploader selection, the fields of the suite hash and the file format are automatically populated, and optionally the field of IPFS URI containing dataset report that is also automatically generated and stored to IPFS by DDM backend services (if uploader selected to include it in the registration). Validation results are submitted by human experts through a dedicated validation dialog (Figure 23b) directly to the ValidationRegistry smart contract. In this dialog, the IPFS URI with results in JSON format, validation hash and success fields are mandatory while IPFS URI containing dataset report is optional. Finally, once all required validations are completed, the reward-claim dialog (Figure 24) allows the uploader to submit the claim transaction and receive the corresponding non-transferable NFT in MetaMask wallet, which also is immediately reflected in the dashboard view.

Figure 23: a) Registering Dataset with Report, b) Submitting Validation for Registered Datasets

Figure 24: Frontend Page: Claim Rewards for Validated Dataset

4.2.7 User Interfaces and Frontend Integration

Two main interface pages were developed to support the NFT provenance mechanism. The first one provides a dashboard for all contract-driven interactions, while the second provides an indexed paginated view of all transaction and event logs depending on user's preferred filtering and sorting options.

4.2.7.1 Dashboard page

The Web3 dashboard is structured as a direct reflection of the deployed smart contract architecture and exposes all on-chain interactions and emitted events in a unified interface, grouped by smart contract. Each smart contract is represented in a panel (presented in Figure 25) that provides: (i) information about its state and callable functions, as well as (ii) governance (Governor Address(es), Registered Signer Address(es)) and (iii) deployment information (network, deployer address, transaction Ids, chain identifier, genesis block). Users can toggle the visibility of emitted events per smart contract independently but also in a similar unified manner, apply filters by block, transaction hash, or parameters, and, last but not least, use contextual buttons with popover descriptions and individual dialog interfaces (Figures 22, 23) to call the corresponding on-chain methods, as described in smart contract section.

Figure 25: Frontend Page: Web3 Dashboard (i)state and callable functions in red and blue frames respectively, (ii) contract and governor related event in yellow and orange frames respectively, (iii) deployment info in green frame)

4.2.7.2 Contracts page

In addition to the dashboard page, the Contracts page provides an indexed and paginated view of all blockchain transactions and emitted events of all smart contracts as replicated in catalogue from DDM event handling services during the whole lifecycle of the deployed contracts. Users can apply advanced filtering and sorting options based on block ranges, transaction, contract addresses, event parameters, and network selection, as presented on Figure 26.

Figure 26: Frontend Page: Contracts Transactions and Events

5 Framework Architecture

In this section, we describe the architecture of the ExtremeXP framework from a functional viewpoint, i.e. in terms of functional components and interactions between them. This viewpoint is complemented by the implementation and deployment viewpoints of the ExtremeXP architecture which will be described in D6.2 “Integrated ExtremeXP Framework”.

5.1 Structural perspective

From a structural perspective, the ExtremeXP framework architecture consists of functional components, i.e. units of functionality, organized into functional modules.

Figure 27: Structural view of functional architecture of ExtremeXP framework.

Figure 27 depicts the **twenty functional components** (in blue) of the architecture, which belong to one of the **five functional modules** (in dashed lines): **User Interface, Experiment Modelling, Experiment Execution, User Interaction, and Knowledge Management**. The last four were already identified in D2.1 [AAB+24]. Table 13 provides an overview of the different functional components.

It is important to note that the framework is a collection of components that are loosely coupled and can be assembled together as needed. Where appropriate, this and the next sections make a distinction between mandatory (i.e. core) and optional (i.e. supplementary) components.

Table 13: Overview of ExtremeXP components.

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
Interface	Portal	The application that provides the starting point and a single point of reference for users of the ExtremeXP integrated framework. Using the portal is not strictly necessary, but it is convenient since all the other components are accessible through it. It is reified as a React web application.	SIN

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
Experiment Modelling	Experiments designer	Web application that enables the specification of experiments, including their control flow and the corresponding exploration spaces, via an intuitive HTML-based interface. The experiments specified via the Experiments Designer are automatically translated into DSL files (inputs to the Experimentation Engine). This component is built with React and is described in detail in Section 4.2.2 of D5.1.	VUA
	Workflow graphical editor	Web application that allows the specification of workflows used in experiments, including the workflow control and data flow and task parameters. The application takes the form of a visual canvas where tasks and datasets can be dragged and dropped and connected together. This component is implemented with React Flow and is described in detail in Section 4.2.1 of D5.1.	VUA
	Intent anticipation	This component provides guidance to end users when constraining the workflows to be generated. Specifically, it provides recommendations by leveraging the information of past experiments stored in a Knowledge Graph by using both fixed SPARQL queries and flexible suggestions coming from the knowledge graph embeddings derived from the graph.	UPC
	Intent specification	Enables non-expert users and data engineers to specify their intents in a guided and human-friendly manner. To do so, the intent specification component relies on the powerful knowledge base expressed as knowledge graph, modeling users, the experimentation domain, and the datasets. End users' intents are translated into complex analytics workflows, accounting for the possibility of multiple solutions to be included into final full experiment specifications (expressed in DSL files).	UPC
	Analytics task library	Provides predefined analytic tasks that correspond to common needs such as data integration, feature selection, and data augmentation. The tasks can be selected by data engineers using the Experiments Editor and/or the Intent Specification Editor and Experiments Generator, configured to match the needs of the CAW, and added to the experiment/intent specifications. The tasks that populate the library are the technical outcomes of WP3 of ExtremeXP.	I2CAT

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
	Options explorer	<p>Supports the decision-making of the optimization algorithms hosted by the Experimentation Engine (and/or of the data engineers controlling a running experiment) on which CAW variants (i.e. dataset, algorithm, model) to run. Based on knowledge from past experiments as well as constraints defined by the scientist, it proposes optimal options (CAW variants) that are more promising to run, hence effectively limiting the variability space of an experiment and speeding up its overall execution. The decision making is based on stochastic methods (i.e. Markov Decision Process), thus the models are trained/calibrated and hosted within this software component to enable accurate and objective decision making.</p>	UL
	DSL editor	<p>The Domain Specific Language (DSL) editor is a fully fledged Integrated Development Environment (IDE) based on Visual Studio Code (VSC). It comprises (1) the DSL framework, (2) the Visual Studio Code extension, and the (3) language server.</p> <p>(1) is an Xtext project that contains the complete grammar definition, validation rules, and scoping logic for the workflow DSL used in this project. It serves as the foundational infrastructure that defines the syntax and semantics of the DSL. The Xtext-generated components provide the parsing, type checking, and cross-reference resolution capabilities necessary for working with the DSL across different tools and editors.</p> <p>(2) is a Visual Studio Code extension that implements a client for the Language Server Protocol (LSP). This extension enables developers to write, edit, and validate workflow DSL code with full IDE support including error highlighting and navigation features.</p> <p>(3) is an as an LSP server, i.e., a centralized service that any LSP-compatible editor can connect to, providing real-time syntax checking, semantic validation, code completion, and other language features.</p>	CUNI

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
	Design model storage	It is a centralized repository that maintains model descriptions and facilitates conversion between different workflow representations, particularly between graphical editor outputs and DSL text formats. This storage system provides an API that enables bidirectional transformation, allowing workflows created in a graphical editor to be converted into DSL code and vice versa. More precisely, when users create or modify workflows or experiments in the graphical editor, the JSON output is translated to DSL format and saved in the Design Model Storage. This ensures that users can switch between visual and textual editing modes seamlessly.	CUNI
Experiment Execution	Experimentation engine	Python library and service for running experiments specified in DSL files provided as inputs. Its functionalities comprise parsing the DSL specifications and orchestrating the execution of experiments as prescribed in the specification. Each experiment takes the form of sequential or parallel execution of the workflows (precisely, workflow variants) pertaining to the experiment. It is a central component that needs to interact both with the Design model storage (to load DSL specifications), with the Executionware (to ask for the execution of workflows) and with the Data abstraction layer (to save metrics produces in experiments).	VUA
	Executionware	This component is responsible for executing workflows. For every workflow provided by the Experimentation Engine, the Executionware executes its tasks in the predefined order (sequentially or in parallel) and evaluates any conditional flows. For each task, it provides the dataset inputs by interacting with the Distributed Dataset Management (DDM). Similarly, it persists every task's output dataset using the DDM. While running a workflow, it periodically (by default every 1 second) sends a progress message to the Experimentation Engine, with information about the execution of the workflow and currently running task(s). The main Executionware of ExtremeXP is based on AE's ProActive Workflows & Scheduling tool and is thoroughly described in Section 5 of D5.1.	AE
User Interaction	Visualisation user interface	The Visualisation User Interface is a web-based component that enables users to monitor, control, and interact with experiments and to visually analyse their results. It supports explorative analytics through interactive visualisations, filters, and comparisons over	ARC

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
		<p>experiment results as well as their inputs. The UI provides real-time monitoring and lifecycle control of experiments and workflows, including starting, stopping, or pausing their execution. Based on the visual analysis of results, users can adjust experiment configurations dynamically, such as modifying scheduling parameters or adding new workflows. In addition, it integrates explainability outputs, allowing users to explore counterfactuals, feature importance, and other explanation results directly within the interface. Finally, it integrates domain-specific visualisation component, such as the 3D VR Flood visualiser developed within ExtremeXP for Use case 1.</p>	
	<p>Visualisation middleware</p>	<p>The Visualisation Middleware acts as an intermediary between the Visualisation UI and the ExtremeXP data repositories, ensuring efficient interaction during the visual exploration and analysis of experiment results and data. It receives requests from the UI for experiment inputs, outputs, and metrics, and coordinates their retrieval, processing, and optimization to deliver responsive interactive visual analysis. To maintain low latency, the middleware applies query optimization, adaptive sampling and aggregation, caching at both memory and file-system levels, and prefetching guided by user interaction patterns and workflow metadata. These mechanisms reduce data transfer overheads from the Decentralized Data Management system and enable smooth, real-time exploration and explainability even when operating on large experimental data.</p>	<p>ARC</p>
	<p>Explainability</p>	<p>A Python-based module that provides on-demand explainability for experiment results. When triggered by the UI, it selects the appropriate method from the Explainability Methods Repository, executes it, and returns the resulting insights for visualisation. Depending on the data and technique, this may involve training a surrogate model, applying global methods such as ALE plots, or generating local explanations such as counterfactuals. The computed explanations are returned to the Visualisation UI and integrated into the user's ongoing visual exploration.</p>	<p>ARC</p>
	<p>Gamification</p>	<p>The role of the gamification component is to process preselected metadata generated in the ExtremeXP experiments to feed individual and collective challenges and generate virtual or real-life rewards that users can check. The overall motivation is to incentivize the users of</p>	<p>I4D</p>

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
		the ExtremeXP framework to specify and run enhanced experiments by enabling competition in a gamified environment.	
Knowledge Management	Data abstraction layer	It is a service for storing data about every executed experiment: it stores the serialized workflow, the pointers to input datasets (which we consider as versioned and thus immutable), parameters used to parameterize the workflow, human-in-the-loop inputs during the experiment, and the generated values for every workflow metric. The underlying model repository has the write-once semantics. Once the workflow is stored in the repository, it cannot be changed or deleted. A permanent URI exists for each executed workflow in the repository, which is recorded in the metadata of datasets and metrics created by the respective workflow. DAL provides both complete traceability of dataset and models and repeatability of experiments.	CUNI
	Access control	Manages the access of users to different datasets and service endpoints across various modules of the architecture. It enforces attribute-based access control (ABAC) based on contextual information and enables the interaction with key knowledge management components like the Distributed Dataset Management and the NFT-based Data Provenance. This component ensures secure access to datasets, experiment specifications, and metrics, maintaining data integrity and confidentiality. Its integration with distributed file systems and DLT enhances security, supports data provenance, and guarantees traceability, aligning with the goal of secure, transparent access in a decentralized environment.	TUD
	Experiment cards	Manages knowledge and documentation of experiments by providing a view and a querying mechanism on lessons learnt from experiments' execution, considering users' perspective. Experiment Cards ensure that the dynamic processes of experimentation are captured throughout the experiment lifecycle both automatically, through metadata-field population whenever applicable and available (e.g. through DAL and DDM), and through human interaction.	ICCS
	Distributed dataset Management	Manages decentralized data and knowledge artefacts that can be used in ExtremeXP experiments. Distributed Dataset Management (DDM) introduces a combination of peer-to-peer data sharing techniques and traditional	ICCS

Module name	Component name	Component description	Responsible partner
		distributed storage solutions to persist and retrieve any datasets considered as input or output of ExtremeXP experiments. The retrieval functionality is supported by powerful catalogue functionalities that consider relevant metadata. In addition, DDM supports the description of dataset expectations that are automatically validated upon upload engaging an LLM-based approach. Last, the overall datasets management is performed in a secure manner through the proper integration to the ExtremeXP ABAC authorization feature.	
	NFT-based data provenance	Attaches metadata to any datasets managed by DDM, in a transparent, immutable, and unique manner, using blockchain technologies. This mechanism introduces a novel approach in characterizing datasets based on a wide range of metadata that are important for inferring the input data quality used in ExtremeXP-based experiments (e.g., unbiased, adequate volume, appropriate quality etc.). Such metadata are appended to DDM-managed datasets in an immutable manner, engaging trustworthy expert human evaluators or third-party services that can automatically extract such data aspects. Along these characteristics, information such as dataset owner(s) and parent dataset(s) used, are attached, through minting process, as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) over a permissioned and private blockchain.	ICCS

5.2 Behavioural perspective

To provide a behaviour/interactions perspective, we will zoom into each module in turn in the rest of this section and provide an overview of how the components of each module interact with each other and with components of other modules.

5.2.1 Interface

Since this module consists of only a single component, the Portal, there is no interaction between components within this module. Instead, the Portal allows the interaction of end-users with all the other modules, as depicted in Figure 28. This figure shows the four user roles that the ExtremeXP framework supports: Data Creator, Data Engineer, Domain Expert, and Gamification Manager. Their actions and responsibilities are described together with the rest of the functional modules in the next subsections.

Figure 28: Interactions of the Interface module

5.2.2 Experiment Modelling

Figure 29: Interactions of the Experiment Modelling module

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Experiment Modelling module are depicted in Figure 28 and described next.

1. The data engineer receives the requirements from the domain expert and specifies experiments and corresponding workflows. There are three options to specify experiments in the ExtremeXP

framework: using the intents tools, the visual editors, and the DSL editor. Before using any of these options, the user needs to be authenticated and authorized via the Access Control component (1.1). Each option is described in the next three steps in turn.

2. The intent tools comprise the Intent anticipation and Intent specification components. Using those tools, the user specifies input datasets and intents (e.g. “find a classifier for a particular column in the dataset”); via a series of transformations, the tools automatically transform such (high-level) intents into workflows and experiments expressed in the DSL of ExtremeXP. In terms of interactions, the Intent Anticipation retrieves the user interaction data from past experiments saved in DAL and uses them internally to predict user intents (2.1). The Intent Specification may also interact with the Option Explorer to retrieve recommendations for workflows to run based on past experiments of the same or other users (2.2). This is further used to involve past data from end users into preselecting the solutions, thus pruning the search space, and personalizing better the final experiment specification.
3. The visual editors comprise the Workflow Graphical Editor and the Experiments Designer. Together, they allow users to model both workflows and experiments that involve such workflows using intuitive graphical (web-based) interfaces. These components provide users with more fine-grained control over the specification of their experiments compared to the intent tools, at the cost of higher specification effort.
4. The DSL editor is a textual editor that can be used for the specification of experiments and encompassing workflows and tasks in the DSL of ExtremeXP, which is textual. Users have the maximum degree of flexibility and expressivity when working with this editor compared to the visual or intent editors. However, there is a learning curve for mastering the DSL. When using the DSL editor, users can optionally select and specify analytics tasks from the Analytics Task Library (4.1). The DSL editor comes with two internal components, the DSL language server, a component that provides the important syntax highlighting and auto-completion functionalities to the editor, and the DSL framework, a component that hosts the meta-model of the DSL.
5. Irrespective of the modelling tool used – intent, visual, or DSL-based – the results of the Experiment Modelling modules are always DSL specifications (.xpp files) stored in the Design Model Storage component. From there, they are loaded by the Experimentation Engine to be executed, as described in the next subsection. The Design Model Storage is also responsible for synchronizing the specifications viewed and produced by the visual editors with the ones of the DSL editor – this takes the form of a bi-directional transformation that allows a user to e.g. start modelling on the visual editors, then switch to the DSL editor, then back to the visual editors etc. (5.1).

Note that at the first half of the ExtremeXP project, a prototype of the Virtual dashboard was implemented with the goal to serve as an alternative means for modelling experiments via a VR interface. This component is not part of the final set of functional components of the ExtremeXP architecture, since at the second half of the project the efforts of the VR research focused on Use case 1 (development of 3D VR Flood Visualiser) where higher potential for impact was foreseen.

5.2.3 Experiment Execution

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Experiment Execution module are depicted in Figure 29 and described next.

Figure 30: Interactions of the Experiment Execution module

1. To start the execution of an experiment, the Experimentation Engine first receives an experiment definition along with corresponding workflow definition(s) (DSL files) that reside in the Design Model Storage. This can be triggered either programmatically, via the Experimentation Engine Python library, or via the web interface of the ExtremeXP portal.
2. Before the start of the execution, the Engine sends the experiment definition to the DAL which persists it into a “new experiment” entry. This caters for replicability of past experiments.
3. Once the experiment is parsed, the Experimentation Engine creates one or more workflows and sends them to the Executionware for execution. The Executionware can typically be configured to run more than one workflow at the same time.
4. Upon receiving a new workflow to run, the Executionware executes it by running its tasks in the specified order. For each task, it retrieves any input datasets from the DDM (4.1), executes the task, and saves any output datasets to the DDM. If the task involves obtaining user metrics, it receives them from the User Interaction module (4.2). The Executionware sends progress messages back to the Experimentation Engine to notify about the progress of the execution of each task (4.3).
5. Upon completing the execution of a whole workflow, the Executionware sends all the obtained metrics (including any user metrics) to the Engine, which in turn persists them in the DAL.
6. At any point during the execution of an experiment, users are able to interfere with a running experiment or workflow to pause, continue, or stop it. On top of this, users can schedule the execution of extra workflows for a running or for a completed experiment.

5.2.4 User Interaction

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the User Interaction module are depicted in Figure 30 and described next.

Figure 31: Interactions of the User Interaction module

1. The User (acting in the role of Data Engineer or Domain Expert) interacts with User Interaction module via the User Interface or the Gamification components. The former are described in steps 2-5 while the latter in step 6.
2. The Visualisation Middleware evaluates the visualisation and explainability request received by the user using its internal Visual Operation Evaluation Engine. First, it tries to optimize the visualisation query considering the user constraints and intents (e.g. use sampling or aggregation). It then checks whether the necessary data are already cached. If not, the DDM provides them to the Visualisation Middleware (2.1). The Access Control component is used to evaluate whether the (authenticated) user has access to the requested datasets (2.2).
3. If explainability aspects are requested by the user in step 1, an explainability request is sent from the Visualisation Middleware to the Explainability component. The latter, via its internal Visual Operation Evaluation Engine, selects the appropriate explainability method to run from the Explainability Models Repository, trains a surrogate model (if needed), runs the explainability method, and returns its results to the Visualisation Middleware.
4. The visualisation and explainability results are combined by the Visual Operation Evaluation Engine of the Visualisation Middleware. At this point, as an extra performance-enhancing step, the Engine may prefetch data for future visualisation and explainability requests.

5. Finally, the Visualisation Middleware sends the combined visualisation and explainability results to the User Interface.
6. Optionally, the users of the ExtremeXP framework can use the Gamification component, which turn the experimentation process into a serious game, where players can claim and win rewards and unlock levels. In particular, the Gamification Manager(s) are responsible for setting up the games to be played by the Domain Expert(s), while The Domain Experts can view their progress in the game(s), leaderboards, and unlock rewards.

5.2.5 Knowledge Management

The internal and external interactions of the components included in the Knowledge Management module are depicted in Figure 31 and described next.

Figure 32: Interactions of the Knowledge Management module

The Knowledge Management module can be seen as a set of services of the ExtremeXP framework that enable the persistence and privacy-preserving storage and access of data from the framework.

Since we have already detailed all the interactions of Knowledge Management with the components of the other three modules in the previous sections, we focus here on the interactions that take place within the module itself. The interactions are just listed below; they do not have to take place in this exact order.

1. As an initial first step, the Data Engineer needs to register the authenticated users and setup the access control policies pertaining both the services and the datasets that the users can access. The policies may refer to multiple contextual attributes (e.g., role, time of request, location of the requestor etc.) that should be evaluated before yielding an access control decision.
2. As a second necessary step, the Data Creator needs to provide the necessary input datasets using the Distributed Data Management. This is necessary for the execution of any experiment. When creating new datasets, the user has to also specify the relevant access control policies which are persisted in the Access Control component (2.1). Also, whenever any dataset is accessed by any service in the framework, the DDM check the relevant user's access via the Access Control component (2.2).
3. Any dataset available through the ExtremeXP distributed file system can have several metadata (i.e., characteristics) attached to it. These characteristics are defined per dataset by either human evaluators or dedicated services or both, in order to create a trustworthy description of the datasets that can be used, through the platform. The NFT-based Data Provenance Mechanism is responsible for attaching a wide range of metadata (e.g., unbiased data, adequate volume, appropriate data quality etc.) on each dataset and minting them transparently and immutably, over a permissioned and private blockchain. In addition, several data provenance-related information (e.g., dataset owner(s), parent dataset(s) used as input etc.) can be attached, as well.
4. As is has been already described in the previous sections, the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) is responsible for saving the experiment definitions and metrics of running or completed experiments.
5. Finally, the Experiments card component is responsible for managing knowledge and documentation of past experiments by organizing all the extracted knowledge in forms amenable to quick and visual user analysis. It takes inputs from both the DDM and the DAL and writes back to DDM (since cards are saved in dedicated files in the filesystem managed by DDM).

5.3 Reference architecture for experiment- and user-driven analytics

The software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework presented in the previous subsections can act as a reference architecture for other frameworks that enable experiment- and user-driven analytics at scale. An organization that would like to use the ExtremeXP framework can use the holistic software architecture presented in this deliverable as a starting point and tailor it to their needs. Practically, this may result in leaving out some of the components or introducing other components that either cover extra functionalities or allow for smoother integrations with other – existing – systems in the organization.

Ideally, we would have compared our architecture and framework with other architectures and frameworks that focus precisely on experiment- and user-driven analytics. Such comparative analysis would have been useful for extracting best practices and common pitfalls on developing such frameworks in future endeavours. However, since this is an emerging domain, it was not possible to find other frameworks that share exactly the same focus as the ExtremeXP one.

At the same time, we observed that:

1. **The majority of the use cases of ExtremeXP focus on complex analytics workflows that take the form of Machine Learning (ML) pipelines.** For instance, UC2 focuses on training a classifier for identifying cyber-attacks, UC3 on selecting the best image identification inference pipeline, and UC5 on training a classifier for time series anomaly detection to enable proactive maintenance.

The remaining two use cases, UC1 and UC4, although they do not feature ML pipelines as the primary focus, they also include ML tasks (e.g. as alternative tasks). Hence, ML workflows and lifecycle management is the common denominator across all the five use cases of ExtremeXP.

2. **ML Operations (MLOps), an industry-driven paradigm for managing the lifecycle of ML pipelines [KKH23], has been growing in importance in the last five years.** Architectures for MLOps systems have started to emerge and be documented in the literature. A wealth of published examples can be studied to derive a reference architecture for this domain.

Given the above, within T2.4 we also analysed the architectures of MLOps systems with the overall aim of contributing to a reference architecture for MLOps systems. To keep the focus of this section on the ExtremeXP framework architecture, we describe the design and the results of the MLOps architectures study in Appendix B.

Although the ExtremeXP framework architecture does not neatly fit under the conceptualization of MLOps architectures in this study, it shares several components especially under the Data Curation, Storage and Versioning, and ML Training categories. The work within ExtremeXP has been focusing on the design time aspects of optimizing CAWs (including and focusing on ML training pipelines). A natural extension of the results, technologies and tools of the project is to support optimization of CAWs at runtime, i.e. deployed in production environments. In such case, our work on conceptualizing and providing a reference architecture of MLOps provides a solid starting point.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable presents the final outcome of the conceptual foundations of ExtremeXP as developed within WP2. More precisely, it describes the results of all four tasks of WP2 (Tasks 2.1-2.4).

The main achievements of this work are the following:

- **Single unified meta-model describing both ExtremeXP workflows and experiments (Task 2.1).** This meta-model now captures the complete range of ExtremeXP concepts: composite workflows, assembled workflows, task specifications, operators, data links, parameters and value domains, metrics, experiment spaces, and experiment-level control structures. Its expressiveness and granularity are validated through all project use cases and through the implementation of the DSL and the graphical editors. The meta-model, which was developed from scratch for the ExtremeXP project, serves as the stable core for all modelling activities and tools in the framework.
- **New domain-specific language (DSL) defined on top of the meta-model (Task 2.2).** This human-readable DSL covers constructs for workflow composition, variability, experiment configuration, and parameter exploration. A language server, integrated with the DSL and exposed via the Language Server Protocol (LSP), enables real-time validation, cross-reference resolution, and semantic checks in Integrated Development Environments (IDEs). This server powers the web-based DSL editor, which allows for specifying experiments and associated workflows in an intuitive and expressive way, even simultaneously by multiple users. Through the integration of the DSL with the experimentation engine of ExtremeXP, workflows and experiments expressed in the DSL can be parsed, validated, transformed into executable workflow graphs, and deployed within the experimentation engine without manual intervention. This confirms that the meta-model and DSL are not only expressive and well-structured but also fully operational and aligned with the overall ExtremeXP architecture.
- **Semantic model and associated probabilistic method for providing recommendations for the experimentation process (Task 2.2).** The semantic model is grounded in the formal language of Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) and represents a probabilistic, experiment-centric knowledge base. Information about datasets, algorithms, models, users, intents, and constraints is encoded as a knowledge graph; the MDPs operate over this graph to rank alternatives and recommend optimal workflows to experiment with. The method operates on domains, intents, and hard and soft constraints provided by users. By (1) combining the knowledge from past experiments with the requirements from users, (2) converting the resulting knowledge graphs into MDPs, and finally (3) solving those MDPs, the method is able to yield optimal policies in the form of ranked lists of recommended options, for example, “optimal algorithms and models for the given dataset under specified constraints”.
- **Flexible and transparent context-aware access control mechanism (Task 2.3).** This mechanism provides a holistic solution for protecting resources (datasets, but also experiment definitions and experiment results) of the ExtremeXP framework. It caters for the multi-domain and decentralized nature of the framework’s deployment in real settings where data analysts and data engineers need to run experiments that span across different administrative domains. The mechanism developed within ExtremeXP allows data analysts and data engineers to execute their experiments and workflows securely, accessing only the resources they are permitted to, through a fine-grained Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) implemented on a blockchain, thereby enhancing trustworthiness and transparency. The mechanism is implemented and demonstrated using the Hyperledger Besu blockchain framework; its performance is assessed through the transaction-time overhead it introduces.

- **Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based dataset provenance mechanism (Task 2.3).** This mechanism provides the means to attach metadata to any datasets managed by the ExtremeXP framework, and precisely via its Decentralized Data Management (DDM) component, in a transparent, immutable, and unique manner, using blockchain technologies. This mechanism introduces a novel approach in characterizing datasets, based on a wide range of metadata that are important for inferring the input data quality, used in ExtremeXP-based experiments (e.g., unbiased, adequate volume, appropriate quality etc.). Such metadata are appended to DDM-managed datasets requests, in an immutable manner, engaging trustworthy expert human evaluators or third-party services that can automatically extract such data aspects. Along these characteristics, information such as dataset owner(s) and parent dataset(s) used, are attached, through minting process, as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) over a permissioned and private blockchain, enabling effective tracking of dataset provenance.
- **Software architecture of ExtremeXP framework (Task 2.4).** The software architecture of the ExtremeXP framework was iteratively developed within the course of the project and took the final shape in the version documented in this deliverable. The final architecture is comprised of twenty functional components grouped into five modules. It continues to provide an important point of reference for project partners in several activities including: synchronization of development activities, integration and testing activities, and communication of the functionalities provided by the ExtremeXP framework to third parties. This deliverable provides a functional view over this architecture, purposely focusing on the roles, responsibilities, and functionalities of each component; D6.3 will detail on the implementation and integration views of the final architecture. Although not intended to work as a direct blueprint, the holistic software architecture of ExtremeXP documented in this deliverable can definitely act as pivot point for the development of specialized architectures that fit the needs of organizations that want to apply scalable experiment- and user-driven analytics.

Appendix B MLOps Reference Architecture

The following subsections provide an overview of the work; more details can be found in the published paper [NBG+24].

Research methodology and process

To derive such a reference architecture for MLOps, we aim at **identifying, classifying, and analysing the architectures of existing MLOps systems described in scientific literature**. To this end, we use the research method of **Systematic Mapping Study (SMS)** as described in established guidelines for systematic secondary studies [KK+07]. The study focuses on the structural views of MLOps architectures, i.e. on the individual components, their dependencies, responsibilities, and the tools that support them.

The study has the overall Research Question (RQ) of “How are MLOps architectures described in the scientific literature?”, which is broken down into the following sub-RQs:

RQ1 Which are the different components and their dependencies?

This RQ helps us categorize the various components within an MLOps architecture and comprehend how different researchers and practitioners interconnect these components.

RQ2 Which tools are used to support or implement the identified components?

This RQ helps us identify tools that can be used for implementing an architecture component, as well as identify the most and the least tool-supported components.

An overview of the research process is depicted in Figure 33. Essentially, we first obtain an initial set of papers via an automated title-focused search on Google Scholar, then filter the results to obtain a starting set of primary studies. After extracting data from the first set of primary studies, we augment this set via bi-directional one-step snowballing and extract data from the new set of primary studies. Using Google Scholar as a meta-engine allows us to avoid bias towards specific publishers [ABA+19]. Finally, the extracted data is used in a rigorous synthesis process.

Figure 33: Overview of the research process

In the **automated initial search** phase, we retrieve all papers returned by Google Scholar using the query:

allintitle: (MLOps OR “machine learning operations”) AND (model OR models OR pipeline OR pipelines OR architecture OR architectures OR architecting OR workflow OR workflows OR process OR processes)

In the **paper selection** phase, we filter papers retrieved in the first phase using the following selection criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- I1 The paper describes the architecture of an MLOps system or part thereof.
- I2 The described MLOps architecture is an original contribution of the paper, not simply cited related work.

Exclusion criteria:

- E1 The paper is not written in English.
- E2 The paper is a shorter or earlier version of a paper that is already included.
- E3 The paper is a pure secondary or tertiary study.
- E4 The full text of the paper is not available.
- E5 The paper is not peer-reviewed and published.

To be included in the list of primary studies, a paper must fulfil all inclusion and no exclusion criteria.

In the **data extraction** phase, we systematically analyse the primary studies and extract data related to the RQs. To refine our data extraction strategy, we first conduct a data extraction pilot on five randomly chosen papers. Data from each paper is extracted by two authors independently and discussed in a consensus meeting leading to the final data extraction framework depicted in Table 14. For RQ1, we extract the items “Architecture or process figures” and “Architecture components”, while we extract “Tools” and “Tool-component mapping” for RQ2. The “Application domain” and the “Author affiliations” are extracted as generic information to use for further analysis. From this point on, each of the remaining papers is assigned to two authors for data extraction. The extracted data is validated through bilateral discussions and consensus between the authors.

Table 14: Data Extraction Framework of MLOps study

RQ	Data Item	Notes
Generic	Application domain	The respective domain the architecture is proposed for
Generic	Author affiliations	Origin of the architecture: academia, industry, or collaboration
RQ1	Architecture or process figures	The list of relevant figures and their types (values can be architecture, process, or combined)
RQ1	Architecture components	The list of components and their relationship
RQ2	Tools	The list of tools that are used or suggested in the paper
RQ2	Tool-component mapping	The list of tools mapped to the components

In the **snowballing** phase, we apply backward and forward snowballing to enrich the results obtained via automated search. During this step, all papers that either cite or are cited by a paper from the starting set are examined for inclusion in the final set of primary studies. We apply both the same selection criteria and data extraction (steps 2 and 3) as for the initial set of papers. In the end, **we extract data from a total of 92 primary studies** (i.e. selected papers).

Finally, in the **data synthesis** step, we harmonize and classify the extracted data per parameter (structural entities, tools, process steps, stakeholders). To achieve this synthesis, we use card-sorting,

a lightweight, collaborative, qualitative analysis technique [Z16]. In particular, we use hybrid card-sorting [5], a combination of open card-sorting (where categories emerge from the data) and closed card-sorting (categories are defined beforehand based on existing taxonomies). We define the initial set of categories based on our background knowledge of MLOps and software architecture and iteratively refine and enrich this set. We conduct the card-sorting in three phases: in the preparation phase, we print all the extracted components on cards; in the execution phase, we sort the cards into meaningful categories and groups and name them; in the analysis phase, we identify the relationships between the identified components and categories. We also disambiguate and group together the extracted tools and derive their mapping to the synthesized architecture components.

The final output is a general architecture of the MLOps workflows from a structural perspective (represented in a UML component diagram), along with a map between tools and components. Lastly, we synthesize the information about the mentioned domains for which the MLOps models are proposed.

Results

The results of our study are based on extracted and synthesized data from 92 papers published between 2020 and the beginning of 2025. This time frame aligns with the emergence and maturation of the MLOps paradigm, which is placed in early 2019 [TOS+20].

We focus here on highlighting important results pertaining to RQ1 – the answer to RQ2, as well as more details on the derived architecture, and detailed study replication material can be found in the related publication [NBG+24].

MLOps Architecture Components and their Dependencies (RQ1.1)

In total, we synthesized 39 unique architecture components by systematically going through all the architecture figures and descriptions contained in our 92 primary studies. These components are domain-agnostic, i.e., they are not tied to a specific application domain. We group the 39 identified architecture components into 6 categories:

- Data Curation entails components responsible for gathering and processing data for the MLOps system.
- Storage and Versioning comprise components responsible for storing, versioning, and managing the data and models in the system.
- ML Training includes components responsible for training and evaluating the ML models, both in the experimentation and production phases.
- CI/CD refers to the category of components responsible for continuously building and deploying ML pipelines, models, and components.
- Inference entails the components responsible for providing predictions, making subsequent decisions, and monitoring the system.
- Infrastructure and Supporting Services comprises infrastructure components that provide system support, e.g., Container Manager, Orchestrator, etc.

Table 15 displays the 39 components by category, their responsibilities, important aliases that we identified for each component name, and the number of papers the component occurred in (from a total of 92 papers).

We combined the synthesized components and their dependencies into a holistic UML component diagram depicted in Figure 34. In this diagram, we introduce five types of architecture components (see legend). **Baseline components** are core components (white components) in an MLOps system. These components form the foundation of the architecture. They were either present in the majority of studied MLOps architectures or were clearly emphasized to provide key responsibilities in the system, i.e., functionality that is of major importance for MLOps workflows and principles. The more

of these baseline components are missing, the less appropriate it becomes to classify the system as an MLOps system. For example, a system with all baseline components except the ML Metadata Repository may still be considered an MLOps system, but removing one or two more baseline components will likely put the system in violation with core MLOps principles.

However, the baseline components need to be complemented with the components of either the **inference service group** (green) or the **inference engine group** (blue) to form a complete MLOps architecture. **Add-on components** represent supplementary components (dotted border) that can be situationally useful or provide complementary capabilities in the MLOps system, e.g., the Model Comparison Runner. As a special type of add-on component, the ones of the **online training group** (yellow) can be added to an MLOps architecture, but always together as a group. Note that the Infrastructure and Supporting Services components are not included in the diagram, since they provide support to the whole system.

The baseline components include the Data Preprocessor, which reads its input from the Raw Data Store and stores its results in the Dataset Repository. The latter provides data to both the Data Labelling Component and the ML Experiment Pipeline. At the same time, the ML Experiment Pipeline (Offline) uses the datasets from the Dataset Repository and the ML algorithms from the Code Repository to train ML models. It then stores the trained ML models in the Model Repository and associated metadata like the training results in the ML Metadata Repository. In case of using pre-trained models instead of training models from scratch, the ML Experiment Pipeline (Offline) is substituted with the Fine-Tuning Module, which is responsible for further training the selected pre-trained models with domain-specific data to improve their performance in specific tasks. After deployment, the Runtime Model Monitor provides real-time model performance data.

Overall, the blueprint for assembling a complete MLOps system involves the above-mentioned baseline components, as well as incorporating either the Inference Service or the Inference Engine group, and potentially the online training group and/or other add-on components, forming one of the four characteristic architecture variants (V1-V4) depicted in the figure. In short, in V1 the architecture contains an Inference Service to serve ML models in a production environment. The Inference Service represents an ML component [MBF+22], i.e., a containerized, deployment-ready ML model wrapped into an API that is usable for predictions. Thus, in this variant, these ML components are built, tested, and packaged by the ML Component Builder, then stored in the Artifact Repository, and finally deployed to production via the ML Component Deployer. On the contrary, V2 architecture variant contains an Inference Engine to serve the trained ML models. The Inference Engine contains a runtime for ML models that allows the dynamic deployment of new models through the ML Model Deployer. Hence, this variant efficiently updates only the ML model instead of always replacing the complete ML component offering more efficient and optimized inference and enhancing performance at the cost of more sophisticated design and implementation w.r.t the Inference Service. While in V1 and V2 the retraining of the models is always manual, V3 and V4 are the equivalent architecture variants that involve automated retraining of models. Essentially, to use the automatic retraining capability provided through the ML Training Pipeline (Online), we need to provide the packaged code of the ML pipelines and deploy them via ML Pipeline Builder and ML Pipeline Deployer, respectively. In this variant, the Trigger, using data provided by the Runtime Model Monitor, submits a periodic or event-based retraining request to the ML Training Pipeline. This automatically retrains a new model and then builds and deploys either (i) a new Inference Service in production – in the case of V3 – or (ii) a new ML model in the Inference Engine – in the case of V4.

In addition to the above main variants, the selection of any combination of the add-on components can result in several additional variants. Table 15 can be consulted for a detailed description of all the other components. As an example, we describe the addition of the Model Comparison Runner: adding this component to either V3 or V4 allows more informed model update decisions. The Model

Comparison Runner compares the performance of a newly trained model in the production environment to the currently deployed models and only deploys it if it performs better than the deployed models. In the absence of this component, the newly trained model is always deployed, even if its performance would be inferior to the current ones.

If we consider the 11 add-on components and the four main variants described above, the selection of any combination between them results in a large number of different architecture variants. Selecting the most suitable variant may depend on factors like specific design decisions, resource availability, scalability considerations, required update frequency, or technological expertise.

Although the ExtremeXP framework architecture does not neatly fit under the conceptualization of MLOps architectures in this study, it shares several components especially under the Data Curation, Storage and Versioning, and ML Training categories. Although the work within ExtremeXP has been focusing on the design time aspects of optimizing CAWs (including, and focusing on ML training pipelines), a natural extension of the results, technologies and tools of the project is to support optimization of CAWs at runtime, i.e. deployed in production environments. In such case, our work on conceptualizing and providing a reference architecture of MLOps provides a solid starting point.

Figure 34: UML component diagram of MLOps architecture variants

Table 15: MLOps architecture components, their aliases, responsibilities, and number of occurrences in primary studies

	Component Name	Aliases	Responsibilities	#
Data Curation	Data Collector	Data Acquisition, Data Loading	Collects raw data like events from various data sources. As a specialized version, Data Generator generates synthetic data with a certain degree of realism instead of collecting real-world data.	19
	Data Source	External Data Sources	Produces and exposes data from a real-world environment, e.g., domain events, IoT sensors, human inputs, etc.	16
	Data Preprocessor	Data Processing, Data Cleaning, Data Validation, Data Curation Pipeline	Validates, cleans, and prepares collected data for storing as ML training datasets.	25
	Data Quality Checker	Data Quality Assessment, Data Quality Monitoring	Evaluates data quality to ensure it satisfies the defined requirements and criteria.	2
	Data Labeler	Data Annotation, Ground Truth Annotation	Adds the ground truth labels for supervised learning models to dataset instances.	6
Storage and Versioning	Data Catalogue	Dataset Catalogue	Stores metadata of datasets in an organized inventory, allows users to browse datasets.	4
	Dataset Repository	Data Store, Data Repository, Data Versioning	Stores and versions the datasets used for ML workflows. As specialized versions, Time-Series DB performs as a repository specialized for time-series data and Vector Database Store saves data in a vectorized manner making actions like retrieval more efficient.	37
	Raw Data Store	Data Store	Stores the raw data that are collected from sources. As a specialized version, Data Lake acts as a centralized raw data store that holds all the data.	14
	Feature Store	–	Computes and stores reusable features, serves computed features with low latency.	16
	Code Repository	Source Code Management, Source Code Repository	Stores and versions the training, deployment, and application source code.	19
	Model Repository	Model Registry, Model Store	Stores and versions the trained ML models along with basic metadata, e.g., their versions, etc.	48
	Artifact Repository	Image Repository, Container Registry	Stores a packaged or containerized ML component that incorporates an ML model for inference.	7
	ML Metadata Repository	Experiment Tracking DB, ML Metadata Store	Stores metadata related to model training and model inference for experiment tracking purposes, e.g., model performance metrics, etc. As a specialized version, Model Provenance DB is a comprehensive metadata store that documents the history and creation of ML models.	32
	Feedback Database	Feedback Store	Stores stakeholder feedback and experiences, e.g., from domain experts or engineers, which are manually considered during iterative model development.	3
Predictions Storage	–	Records the predictions of the deployed model in inference. This storage can be utilized for tracking predictions and explainability.	1	
ML Training	Feature Engineering Pipeline	Feature Selection	Selects and transforms the features of the used dataset for model training.	8
	ML Experiment Pipeline (Offline)	ML Pipeline (Offline), Manual ML Pipeline, Data Science Experiments	Develops, trains, and validates ML models at design time (more experimental and manual).	29
	ML Training Pipeline (Online)	Continuous Training Pipeline, Incremental Online Learning, MLOps Pipeline	Continuously trains ML models at runtime in a production environment (completely automated).	28
	Model Evaluator	–	Evaluates the prediction performance of the models during training.	8
	Fine-Tuning Module	Model Fine-Tuning	Trains the selected pre-trained models with domain-specific data to improve their performance in specific tasks.	2

CI/CD	ML Pipeline Builder	Build And Test Pipeline, CI Tool	Builds, tests, and packages (e.g., in containers) the code of the ML pipeline.	6
	ML Pipeline Deployer	Pipeline Deployment, ML Training Pipeline Deployment, CD Tool	Deploys the (built and packaged) code of the ML pipeline to staging or production environments.	5
	ML Model Deployer	Model Deployment, Deployment Pipeline	Deploys the trained model packaged with the dependencies (e.g., required libraries, preprocessing code, etc) to the production environment.	6
	ML Component Builder	Build Automation Pipeline, Continuous Integration (CI)	Builds and tests ML components, i.e. deployment-ready artifacts (containerized ML models).	9
	ML Component Deployer	ML Deployment, Continuous Delivery, Continuous Deployment, CI/CD Pipeline	Deploys the ML components (containerized ML models) to staging or production environments.	14
Inference	Inference Service	Model Inference, Production ML Service, Model Server	Serves the trained models to provide new predictions.	26
	Inference Engine	Pool Inference, Local Inference Engine, Model Serving Component	Provides an engine that includes an ML runtime into which trained models can be dynamically deployed to serve predictions.	13
	Runtime Model Monitor	Performance Monitor, Monitoring Component, Model Runtime Monitor	Observes continuously the model-serving performance and infrastructure in real-time, and optionally notifies the responsible stakeholders, or signals the 'Trigger' component based on defined criteria.	32
	Trigger	Retraining Triggering Webhook, Retraining Trigger	Triggers retraining of the ML models based on a predefined performance threshold or predefined events and intervals.	13
	Model Comparison Runner	Model Comparison Runner, Model Metrics Evaluator	Compares the newly trained model to the old model and deploys the better-performing one.	3
	Decision Processor	Decision Processing	Derives decisions based on the predictions of the model. The decisions are then acted upon by the actors inside or outside the system.	3
	XAI Module	Explainability Module	Provides interpretable explanations of model decisions to support transparency, trust, and regulatory compliance across the MLOps lifecycle.	2
Infrastructure and Supporting Services	Resource Manager	Resource Leasing, Model Engine	Provides foundational hardware and software computational resources. The provided computational resources can be distributed or non-distributed and scalable or non-scalable.	6
	Communication Middleware	Message Queue, Event Streaming Bus	Distributes the received requests and model predictions to resources. As a specialized version, MQTT Broker acts as a lightweight, publish-subscribe messaging protocol that handles requests as messages.	6
	Container Orchestrator	Container Service, Container Manager	Bundles the model with all of its related files, configurations, and dependencies to run it efficiently across different environments running the same container's engine.	3
	Workflow Orchestrator	Adaptive Scheduler, Workflow Orchestration, Job Tracking Module	Provides system-wide orchestration, decides the execution schedule of multiple models balancing throughput and latency and informs the data requirement of each model to the data coordinator.	12
	Log Manager	Logging, Info Collector, Object Store, Predictions Store	Records and saves the information about running the services, training, user requests, predictions, etc.	6
	API Gateway	–	Provides interaction between the components within the platform and also between the platform and external entities.	8
	MLOps User Interaction Manager	Ops Dashboard, Front-End	Provides interaction between the users and the MLOps platform. This component includes the visualization tasks such as data characteristics and monitoring results (data, model, ...).	10

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